
Gorkhas in Northeast India: Historical Narratives of Conflict and Peacebuilding for Contemporary Conflict Resolution

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ARTICLE DETAILS

Research Paper

Keywords:

Army, Gorkha, Gorkhali, History, India, Nation, Northeast, Peace, Political, Resolution, Treaty and War.

ABSTRACT

This study investigates the historical role of the Gorkhas in Northeast India, focusing on their involvement in both conflicts and peacebuilding efforts. Originating from Nepal, Due to their involvement in the Anglo-Nepalese War and other international conflicts like the World Wars, the Gorkhas came to be known as a "martial race" when they were initially included into British colonial military forces in the early 19th century. Over time, the Gorkhas were integrated into the socio-political fabric of Northeast India, particularly in states like Assam, Manipur, Nagaland, and Meghalaya. Their settlement in these regions led to their active involvement in both military and civilian life, where they contributed to both regional security and socio-economic development. In order to maintain law and order in the unstable tribal areas of Northeast India, the Gorkhas have historically been positioned as important participants in regional military operations. This is especially true of their participation in the Assam Rifles and other security forces. By tracing the Gorkhas' legacy, this study highlights their evolving role from conflict participants to agents of peace and stability in the region. It emphasizes their contribution to curbing insurgencies and maintaining security in areas prone to ethnic and tribal tension, reflecting how their military background has been an advantage for both conflict engagement and resolution. The paper also delves into the role of historical narratives both oral and written in shaping the identity of the Gorkhas and their place in the socio-political

history of Northeast India. It explores how these narratives has been constructed, rewritten, and at times distorted, particularly in the context of contemporary conflicts. In many instances, historical accounts have been used to justify ongoing tensions, but they also offer opportunities for peacebuilding when critically re-examined. This paper suggests that a deeper understanding of these historical narratives is essential for developing more effective conflict resolution strategies in the region. This study aims to contribute to the seminar's broader goal of fostering a nuanced understanding of how history can be used as a tool for peace. By examining the Gorkhas' historical role, it offers insights into how historical legacies can be harness to promote reconciliation and peace in Northeast India, a region marked by complex ethnic diversity and socio-political challenges. Through this critical analysis, the paper advocates for the use of historical narratives as a means of healing divisions and fostering lasting peace in the region.

Introduction: Native to the Indian subcontinent, the Gurkhas/Gorkhas, also known by their last name Gorkhali, are soldiers who primarily live in Nepal and some regions of North India. The Hindu warrior Saint Guru Gorakhnath, who lived in the mountain village of Gorkha, Nepal, in the eighth century, is the source of the name Gorkhas (or Gurkhas). Indian Gorkhas hold permanent Indian citizenship in India, and the term "Gorkha" is used to differentiate between Nepali citizens who reside in India and Indian Gorkhas who are Indian citizens. In addition to their diaspora in other regions of India and outside, they primarily reside in the states of Sikkim, West Bengal, Northeast, and Uttarakhand. According to the Government of India's gazette announcement on the subject of Indian Gorkha citizenship, Indian Gorkhas are consider permanent citizens of India. Myths about the Gorkha in modern-day India, Nepal, and Britain are historicized in this entry. It traces the socioeconomic causes of migration and military duty in Nepal, the magnitude of Nepalese military participation during World War I, and the creation of the Gorkha through British colonial fantasies of the martial race.

1. **From where do they originate? :** The Gorkhas are from Nepal, a landlocked nation bordered to the north by China and to the south by India. In addition, Nepal is well known for being the birthplace of Buddha and the location of Mount Everest.

2. **The formation of the Gurkha:** The colonial Indian Army discovered that the Gurkhas were one of at least a dozen "martial races" living in British India. The establishment of formal ethnologies of castes, nationalities, and faiths eligible for military service preceded the 1902 unification of the Indian Army from three Presidency Armies. In contrast to the majority of Indians who "had neither moral aptitude nor physical courage the courage we should talk of colloquially as 'guts,'" many "Handbooks for the Indian Army" assist military recruiters in identifying the proper type of recruit: those who "had the physical courage necessary for the warrior." In addition to distinguishing between "martial" and "non-martial" Indians in South Asia, the Handbooks and the literature they were linked with separated those who were currently suitable for recruitment from those who had previously been, and made inferences about those who might eventually become sufficiently "martial." This process of entexting fantasies of colonial masculinity led to the development of the Gorkha concept. Their opposition to the alleged vices plaguing the former imperial heartland, which had shown itself to be disloyal during the 1857 "Mutiny", characterized Gorkhas. According to reports, Gorkhas lived in or had family ties to the Gorkha district in central Nepal, where they "knew little, and cared less, about the political changes and evolutions" of Indian nationalisms. This is consistent with all newly discovered "martial races" in the late 19th and early 20th centuries. A note of ambiguity accompanies every bold claim of Gorkha character, mannerisms, and ethnic and geographic origins: some of the works "are undoubtedly incomplete and perhaps in part incorrect" and "these large generalizations are patronizing." Gorkhas took pride in their "Protestant Hinduism" and disdain for the "orthodox Brahman of Banaras." Additionally, they were portrayed as little Englishmen, complete with obscene descriptions of their strong bodies and "delight in all manly sports – shooting, fishing, putting the shot, playing quoits, or foot-ball." Such methods cannot provide a sense of the Gorkha. Many Nepali communities—including, for a while, Garhwalis, who were not even Nepalis — were nonetheless; consider Gorkhas despite having no ties to the Gorkha district or even central Nepal. The sole consistent description of the Gorkhas' racial origins and characteristics was that they were all wiry, robust, broad-headed, and thick skulled. Other descriptions included "Mongoloid," "Caucasian," and "Indo-Tibetan." In addition, there is disagreement over which caste the ideal Gorkha should be from, ranging from the "aboriginal" Magars, Gurungs, Khumbu, and Limbus to the high-caste Rajput Thakurs.
3. **The Fiction of Gorkhas:** Gorkha was and still is fiction, which is why there is this mistake. No group in Nepal identifies as Gorkhas, nor are other Nepalis referring to them as such. Lahure, the

colloquial corruption of Lahori, was and still is the most widely used term for soldiers serving in foreign armies. It refers to Nepali nationals who apply for service in the Lahore courts. Alludes to the pre-colonial South Asian labour market exploitation. The Punjab, the dominion of Ranjit Singh (1780-1839). The increasing number of rural landless people in Nepal throughout the 19th century served as a motivator for joining the Indian army and migrating to Bengal, Assam, and Burma's tea and timber plantations. Nevertheless, until the 1940s, there were only a small number of Nepalese drafted into the Indian army. 55,589 Nepalis, for instance, were drafted into 32 battalions of the Gurkha Rifles and 4 battalions of the 70th Burma Rifles during World War I in order to supplement and replace the 17,000-strong Gorkha army that existed prior to the conflict. Comparing the figure to other colonial forces or even other "martial classes" that the Indian Army recruited, it was noteworthy but by no means excessive. However, the First World War was essential in validating the myth of Gorkhas and further hiding the truth. The battle has been reframed as a setting where Gorkhas were the most common recruited "martial class," and the image of the barbaric, unforgiving Gorkha was (and still is) packaged and marketed in the imperial memorabilia of the time (from the Empire Annual for Boys to subsequent "Johnny Gorkha" action figures). The political, economic, and cultural realities that Nepali soldiers truly experienced are mask by this. In order to meet British quotas, Chandra Shamsher (1863–1929), the Rana or Prime Minister of Nepal, deliberately sent enslaved captives (slavery was abolish in Nepal in 1925). To express their support for the dictatorship in Nepal, village headmen and landowners would frequently send the poorest or most indebted villagers into the army, as Mary des Chenes has demonstrated. After serving in the imperial military, Nepali soldiers frequently returned bitter: "What do the young men know? Nothing! We observed these recruiters' warm "sweaters" and several rupees in their pockets. They assured us that we would go to new areas and eat rice every day. What war-related knowledge did we have? Nothing. The recruiters only discussed pensions, food, and clothing with us; they never discussed war. They were astute. What do you know about the hardships of leaving home when you are young?"

4. **Castes and ethnic groups**: The Indian Gorkhas are an indigenous ethnic group distributed over several northern states of the country and are made up of a variety of castes and ethno-tribe clans. Khas-Parbatiyas like the Bahun (hill Brahmin), Chettri (Khas), Thakuri, Badi, Kami, Damai, Sarki, Gandarbha, and others are among the ethnic groups that make up the Gorkhali Parbatiyas. The Tamang, Gurung, Magar, Newar, Bhujel (Khawas), Sherpa, and Thami are further Tibeto-ethnic tribes. Khumbu (Rai), Limbu (Subba), Sunuwar (Mukhia), Yakkha

(Dewan), Dhimal, and others are Kiratis. The Nepali language, written in Devanagari script, is the common tongue of the Gorkhas, despite the fact that each of them speaks a different language (either an Indo-Aryan or a Tibeto-Burman language). One of India's official languages, it is listed in the eighth Schedule of Indian Constitution.

5. **Population:**

Nepali speakers in India by year.

Census	Nepali speakers	Growth
1971	1,419, 835	-
1981	1,360,636	-4.17
1991	2,076, 645	+52.62
2001	2,871, 749	+38.29
2011	2,926,168	+1.89

Table 1.1: Highlighting the growth of Nepali speakers in India.

According to the 1991 census, the Gorkha population is found in Assam (30.58%), Sikkim (32.05%), Uttarakhand (255.53%), Arunachal Pradesh (16.93%), Himachal Pradesh (50.64%), Maharashtra (59.69%), Meghalaya (6.04%), Manipur (1.08%), Nagaland (6.04%) and Mizoram (8.50%). According to the 2011 census, the state with the largest Gorkha population is West Bengal with a total population of 12.97%, Assam (5.56%), Sikkim (12.87%), Uttarakhand (16.86%), Arunachal (00.42), Himachal Pradesh (27.37%), Maharashtra (19.22%), Manipur (38.61%), Meghalaya (4.91%), Nagaland (27.06%), and Mizoram (0.51%).

6. **Facts about Gurkhas or rather Gorkhas:**

- i. Gorkha is a Sanskrit word, which means Protector of Cows, Gau means Cow and Raksha means Protector.
- ii. Of the 75 districts of contemporary Nepal, Gorkha is one. The idea that the Gorkha people got their name from the Gorkha region of Nepal is false. After the Gorkhas took control of the area, the territory was dub Gorkha. Some of Bappa Rawal's descendants travelled further east in the early 1500s and overran a minor state in modern-day Nepal, naming it Gorkha after their patron saint. Region. Some of Bappa Rawal's descendants travelled further east in the early 1500s and overran a minor state in modern-day Nepal, naming it Gorkha after their patron saint.

- iii. "Jai Mahakali, Ayo Gorkhali" (Hail Great Goddess Kali, Here Comes Gorkhali) is the Gorkha war cry.
- iv. The Gorkha people, who come from Nepal and Northeast India, are named after the Hindu warrior-saint Guru Gorakhnath, who lived in the eighth century. His disciple Bappa Rawal, who was born Prince Kalbhaj /Prince Shailadhis, established the Mewar family. Bappa Rawal's descendants then relocated further east to establish the Gorkha family, which in turn established the Kingdom of Nepal.
- v. The British classified the Gorkhas as a Martial Race. British Indian officials coined the term "Martial Race" to refer to "races" (peoples) who were believed to be inherently aggressive and warlike in combat and who possessed traits like bravery, loyalty, self-reliance, physical prowess, resilience, orderliness, diligence, fighting tenacity, and military strategy. These Martial Races were a major source of recruits for the British colonial army.
- vi. The Gorkhas allege ancestry from the Hindu Rajput's and Brahmins of Northern India, who migrated westward into present-day Nepal. The renowned Bappa Rawal, a Rajput prince-disciple of Guru Gorakhnath, was born Prince Kalbhaj, the founder of the Mewar house, who went on to become the first Gurkha and is considered to be the progenitor of the current Nepalese royal dynasty.
- vii. According to the tradition, Bappa Rawal discovered the warrior saint while hunting in the Rajasthan jungles with pals while he was a teenager in hiding. Bappa Rawal made the decision to remain and tend to the warrior saint, who was meditating deeply. Guru Gorakhnath was pleased with Bappa Rawal's dedication when he woke up. The Guru gave the renowned curved dagger used by modern-day Gurkhas, the Kukri knife, to him. According to the tradition, he informed Bappa that he and his people would now be known as Gurkhas, the followers of Guru Gorakhnath, and that their valour would make them famous across the world. After that, he gave Bappa Rawal and his Gorkhas orders to halt the Muslims' invasion.
- viii. By 1769, the Gorkha dynasty had seized control of what is now Nepal under the direction of Sri Panch Maharaja Dhiraj Prithvi Narayan Shahdev (1769–1775). They established Hinduism as the official religion, but with strong Gorakhnath and Rajput martial elements. As a result, Nepal as it exists now was established as a single country and kingdom.
- ix. Although there are racial differences in Nepal, a Gorkha can belong to any caste, creed, or race. However, only Hindus, including Nepalese Buddhists, are eligible to be Gorkhas because it is

mandatory to adhere to the teachings of Guru Gorakhnath and the Ancient Hindus' Warrior Code. One cannot cultivate a Gorkha's mind-set, spirit, essence, and soul without these lessons.

- x. Even yet, the term "Hinduism" is used to refer to a broad range of Vedic and non-Vedic religions practiced throughout the subcontinent. It is important to note that several ethnic tribes of the Gorkhas also practice the Bon-religion, which is animistic and shamanistic, and should therefore be consider a component of Gorkhali culture.
- xi. Gorkhas from well-known families declined to serve as soldiers but went on to become officers in the British-Indian military. The typical Gorkha peasant, farmer, or villager joins as a soldier. One Gorkha, the great-grandson of Sri Teen Maharaja Jung Bahadur, joined the Gorkha Rifles as an officer and, although still a young captain in the British Indian Army, advanced to the position of aide-de-camp (A.D.C.) to Lord Mountbatten, the final Viceroy of India. In addition to preserving their country's sovereignty, Gorkhals continued to look for work in both Indian and British forces as officers and soldiers after the British left India.
- xii. Today's British Gorkhas are not consider mercenaries under international law; rather, they are fully integrated troops of the British Army who serve in Brigade of Gorkha battalions and follow the same rules and regulations as all other British soldiers. Gorkhas who serve in the Indian Army are subject to similar regulations.
- xiii. “You were my comrades, the obstinate and unyielding Nepalese peasants, and I think of you as I write these final lines. I hear again how you welcomed every challenge with laughter. I see you again, in your bivouacs or around your fires, in the trenches or on a forced march, now shivering with cold and wetness, now burnt by a merciless and blazing sun. You suffer hunger, thirst, and wounds without complaining, until finally your steady lines vanish into the smoke and fury of combat. You are the most generous of the generous, the bravest of the courageous, and the country's most devoted friend. -Professor Sir Ralph Turner, MC, a member of the Queen Alexandra's Own Gurkha Rifles' third unit, participated in the First World War.
- xiv. “The Gurkhas have fought in Britain's conflicts and maintained peace for more than 180 years. They serve in the majority of the 20th century's major conflicts and have receive 13 Victoria Crosses. (The most prestigious and highest honor bestowed upon British and Commonwealth forces for valour in the face of the enemy is the Victoria Cross.)
- xv. We would have to remain silent for two weeks if there was a minute of silence for each Gurkha killed in World War II alone.

7. Gorkhas in India's northeaster states:

- i. **Arunachal Pradesh:** According to the 2001 Census, the districts with the highest Gorkha populations are West Kameng (18.2%), Lohit (15.77%), Dibang Valley (26.77%), Koronu (55.35%), Kibithoo (50.68%), Sunpura (42.28%), Vijoynagar (42.13%), and Roing (32.39%). The 2011 Census shows that the districts with the largest Gorkha populations are West Kameng (17.1%), Lohit (13.77%), Dibang Valley (22.99%), Koronu (48.49%), Kibithoo (6.5%), Sunpura (34.47%), Vijoynagar (41.8%), Sunpura (32.4%), Kibithoo (6.5%), Kibithoo (6.5%), Vijoynagar (41.8%), and Roing (26.0%).
- ii. **Assam:** Sonitpur (6.43%), Tinsukia (7.91%), and Karbi Anglong (5.69%) were home to the Gorkha population in 1991, while Sonitpur (7.81%), Tinsukia (7.64%), Karbi Anglong (5.76%), Sadiya (27.51%), Na Duar (16.39%), Helem (15.43%), Margherita (13.10%), and Umrangso (12.37%) were home to the Gorkha population in 2001. Gorkha people in Sonitpur (7.04%), Tinsukia (7.52%), Karbi Anglong (5.38%), Sadiya (26.2%), Na Duar (14.88%), Helem (14.35%), Margherita (13.47%), and Umrangso (12.46%) were counted in the 2011 Census.
- iii. **Manipur:** The number of Gorkha people in Manipur was 13,571 in the 1961 census, 26,381 in the 1971 census, 37,046, 46,500 in the 1991 census, and 45,998 in the 2011 census. The 2011 census also showed that the Gorkha people were concentrated in Sadar Hills West (33.0%), Saitu-Gamphazol (9.54%), Lamshang (10.85%), Senapati (8.15%), Imphal West (2.01%), and Imphal East (1.51%).
- iv. **Meghalaya:** As per the 1961 census, there were 32,288 Gorkha people living there. According to the 2011 census, the majority of Gorkha people live in the following districts: East-Khasi Hills (4.48%), Ri-bhoi district (4.07%), Myliem (8.18%), Umling (6.72%), Shillong cantonment (29.98%), Shillong (9.83%), Pynthorumkhrah (7.02%), Nongmynsong (26.67%), Madantring (17.83%), and Nongkseh (14.20%). This is in 2011.
- v. **Mizoram:** There are 9,035 Gorkhas in Mizoram, according to the 2011 Census. 5,944 of these, or 1.9% of the total population, are located in the Aizawl district's Tlangnuam Tehsil.
- vi. **Nagaland:** The majority of Gorkha people live in the districts of Kohima (3.66%) and Dimapur (5.70%). Naginimora (7.48%), Merangmen (6.78%), Niuland (6.48%), Kuhoboto (7.04%), Chümoukedima (7.07%), Dhansiripar (6.09%), Medziphema (9.11%), Namsang (8.81%), Kohima Sadar (6.27%), Sechü-Zubza (5.03%), and Pedi (7.61%) were the tehsils with the highest concentration.

vii. **Sikkim**: The population of Gorkha in Sikkim was 610,577 in the 2011 census, although it has increased by about 100,000 since then. Sikkim is the only state in India where the majority of the population is ethnically Nepali. Sikkim's primary language is Nepali/Gorkhali; however, some regions also speak Lepcha and Tibetan (Bhutia). Both the Limbo (53,703) and Tamang (37,696) of Sikkim speak Nepali as their mother tongue, according to the 2011 census. The Bhutia and Lepcha also speak Nepali.

8. **The Gorkha Diaspora's History in Northeast India:**

i. **Assam**: According to Puranic history, Nepal and Kamarup (Assam) were part of a single area known as Matsyendranath. A famous mystical yogi from Kamarup is said to have travelled to Nepal and made his home there. The 19th century saw the revival of this historic connection between Assam and Nepal. Originally, from the Assam valley, the Gorkhas were pastoralists, and their grazing grounds stretched from Baralimara to Bhavani Devi. In 1881, Tezpur's Bula Chapari was designated as a specialized grazing reserve. Following the prosperity of the tea farms in Assam in 1853, the East India Company started hiring Nepali labourers. In 1863, certain rules were passed that allowed Nepalese citizens unrestricted access to Assamese tea estates. Assam's Gorkha population grew organically and began to diversify into dairying and agriculture. The Gorkha range was mainly used to defend oil reserves in 1889, when oil drilling was taking place in Digboi, Assam. However, because the locals were afraid of incursion into the jungles surrounding Digboi, Gorkhas were also deployed for operational operations. The original inhabitants of the areas surrounding Digboi, including Itavati, Rapati, Nalapatti, Muliabari, and Gorkhas, were all Tobasti and Goru Pathak on the Agreement Line. Jitbahadur Pradhan was given permission to hire labourers for the oil refineries in 1923, and he did so by bringing in hundreds of Nepali labourers, mostly from Doors and the Darjeeling Hills. Many of those individuals make Digboi their permanent home by settling there.

ii. **Nagaland**: Hari Prasad Gorkha Rai, a specialist in the Gorkha community in north eastern India, discusses the rise of the Gorkhas in Nagaland. He claimed that approximately 400 years ago, three extremely exhausted and hungry Gorkha lads were encountered by a group of men from the Nagaland village of Chiechama while they were on their way to the fields. The villagers, who felt sorry for them, took them home. The surviving boy claimed to be named "Rai" after two of the boys passed away from cholera a few days later. A village elder who eventually wed his

daughter adopted him. Rai was eventually assimilated into the Angami tribe, and his descendants are today known as the non-Angami Methama clan or Meta Tophris. To honor the clan's founding father, the tribe still maintains the tradition of naming a male kid Rai. In Kohima, the capital of Nagaland state, there is a monument on the grounds of the third Assam Rifles that honor the station's founding in 1835. Accordingly, Nagaland has been inhabited by Gorkhas ever since. Many of these Gorkha troops stayed behind and were rehabilitated at an area known as Chan Mali (shooting range) in Kohima after the British forces entered the city with the native Gorkha infantry, the Cachar Levy, and the artillery soldiers. The same place is still inhabited by their descendants.

iii. **Manipur:** The Gorkhas first arrived in Manipur and settled there around 1819. Before this date, some of the dispersed Nepali families most likely had already made Manipur their home. According to some academics, the Gorkhas of Manipur have been around since the early 16th century. Tradition has it that the first Nepalese arrived in Manipur at the beginning of the tenth century. Kumbi, a Meitei girl from the Mayang Heikong Ningol clan, was the woman he married. His ancestors are known as Gotimayan because this man raised cows and buffaloes in the Khuti (goth-cowshed). During Raja Gambhir Singh's reign in 1824, the first Gorkhas arrived in Manipur. The Gambhir Singh police levy was apply to the Gorkhas of the 16th Sylhet Regional Battalion (later the 8th Gorkha Rifles) at this time. Manipur was severely damage by Burmese invaders and their forces in the first quarter of the 1800s. In 1825, Gambhir Singh organized an army and recruited Gorkhas from Sylhet to guard the frontiers. The Victoria Paltan was the name of this militia. The term Paltan, which is a Nepali corruption of the English train, makes it obvious that the Gorkhas were in charge of the military during this time. Once the British trusted the Gorkha warriors, they were careful to safeguard. The Assam Military Police at the start of the 20th century recruited Gorkhas. Of these, 82 were assign to the Garo Hills Battalion in Tura, 730 to the Lakhimpur Battalion in Dibrugarh, 331 to the Naga Hills Battalion in Kohima, 111 to the Silchar Battalion in Silchar, and 105 to the Dhaka Battalion in Dhaka. As a result, there are still many Gorkha people living in these places, but it is unclear what happened to them in Dhaka following the division. When the battalion was transfer to Europe in 1915, the Darang Military Police took the position of the second Gorkha Rifles, which was station in Imphal. In 1917, the Manipur-based Darang Military Police were transform into the fourth Assam Rifles, which also had 80%. After retiring from active duty, nearly all of the Gorkhas that arrived in Manipur made their home there. In Thangmaiband and later in special colonies in

Eroisembe, Chink, Tangri, Kalapahar, Torbung, Maram, Imphal, Irang, and Kanglatombi, the British government gave land to the members of the Fourth Assam Rifles. Many Gorkha employees of INA also settled in Manipur after 1945. Tula Chand Alay published Manipur KO Sawai, the first poem in Nepali language, in Imphal in 1894. It demonstrates how the Gorkhas were completely integrated into Manipur society and manage to preserve their unique literature while living in the culturally vibrant Meitei society.

- iv. **Mizoram:** For at least 150 years, the Gorkhas have resided in Mizoram. Colonel T.H. Lewin wrote in 1865, "I had developed a strong regard for the small Gorkhas, who, under Col. Macpherson, had carried out the expedition's fighting, and I was granted authorization to send a party to Nepal and recruit immigrants from there to colonize this frontier waste." Gorkha colonies were established on the Myani River, a northern affluent of the Karnaphuli, which is now in Bangladesh, possibly as a follow-up. In order to draw a clear border between the local and British areas, Colonel Lewin intended to build a number of communities along the plains and hills. He also notes that the area where the villages were situated had previously been uninhabited due to fear of the Lushais' raids. My plan was to create a strong stockade of brave, inflexible people, such as the Gorkhas, to act as a barrier between the Mong Raja's domain and the autonomous Lushais to the east. Peace was restored in the majority of the hills following the erection of stockades at Lunglei and Aizawl. The government once again sought after the Gorkhas in Nepal when it needed labourers for jobs like farmers, traders, masons, darkeners, chowkidars, and so on. This was especially true when they were concerned that the locals were not yet completely obedient, or antagonistic. As members of the Frontier Police Battalion, the Gorkhas also made it to Mizoram. In 1872, the Gorkhas saved Mary Winchester, the daughter of the Alexandra pore Tea Garden's manager, who had been kidnapped by the Lushais chieftains. The British trusted the Gorkhas because of their loyalty, and they advised them to make the land their permanent home. In 1889, General Tre Gears raised the Surma Valley Military Police Battalion, which would subsequently become the first Assam Rifles, in Changsil in the north Lushais Hills. Its ranks were mostly occupied by Gorkha troops. Following their retirement from the army, police, and Assam Rifles, the Gorkhas embraced the Lushais Hills as their homeland and are now the most socially cohesive Gorkha group in north-eastern India.
- v. **Meghalaya:** The founding of three Gorkha social organizations in Shillong—the Gorkha Thakur Bari in 1824, the Gorkha Durga Puja Committee in 1872, and the Gorkha Union in 1886—is the first documented indication of the Gorkhas' settlement in Meghalaya, formerly known as the

Khasi-Jaintia Hills. In terms of chronology, the Thakur Bari seems to be the oldest Gorkha organization in the whole Northeast. It continues to operate one girls' middle school and two temples. The Gorkhas from the first and second battalions of the eight GR. founded the Gorkha Durga Puja Committee. The committee was turned over to the civilians and former service members living in and around Shillong in 1940 when the battalions were moved to Quetta, which is today in Pakistan. The Gorkha is another earlier organization. A great deal about the Gorkhas in Meghalaya may be learned from the history of the eighth Gorkha Rifles. According to Major Alban Wilson, Subedar Deoraj Alay, who was granted the civil authority of a third-class magistrate, led the regiment's establishment of an outpost in the Khasi Hills at Umbai in 1845. However, he passed away in Umbai, Cheerapunji, after two years. But in that short period, he had become so beloved by the locals that they built a big tomb over his burial by the side of the road. Even now, every resident of the area worships at his grave and gives it a chew of supari (beetle nut) when they pass by. Garo Hills' commissioner was Lieutenant W.J. Williamson, who was appointed in 1866. Gorkhas from Goal Para, Assam, made up the majority of the coolies and constables transported to Tura. The Gorkhas also worked on building roads and chopping trees. When twelve Gorkhas were gathered and transported from Dhubri, Assam, by American missionaries in route to the Garo Hills. On December 12, 1876, A. G. Phillips, one of the missionaries, wrote in his diary. Shillong, which came to be renowned as the Scotland of the East, seems to have developed in large part thanks to the Gorkhas. Captain Kālu Thapa said that there were no rats in the area when he marched into Shillong with the fourth battalion, 8 GR. Gorkhas were encouraged to relocate to the Northeast along with the service members. Tura-based author Shira, who writes, reveals Red Lynd This: "There was hardly anything out here when Tura was originally taken by the American Baptist Mission in 1876. The school's current location was a dense jungle, teeming with ferocious elephants who wandered freely and broke the stillness with their trumpeting voices. A Nepali man named Goshai at some point in the early years of this century must have inhabited this piece of land. He must have received an invitation from the British government to establish a cattle farm here with the intention of providing milk to the local population. Until recently, Goshai's grazing farm was refer to as Nippal, or "Nepali hill." There were 1,363 people living in Shillong in 1872, 935 of them were serving. 772 Gorkhas served in the armed forces. Although they did not fully inhabit any one location, the Nepalis had established themselves in practically every part of Meghalaya by this point. The poem Tirthavali, written in 1915 by Manorath Upadhyaya, a Jemadar of the Garo Hills Military

Police Battalion, indicates that, similar to Manipur and the Gorkhas in the Garo and Jaintia Hills, modern-day Meghalaya has established itself and is following its own culture, traditions, and literature.

9. **Gorkha recruitment**: Political agent William Fraser and David Ochterlony were quick to see the possibilities of Nepalese soldiers serving in the British military. The British were eager to recruit Nepalese army defectors as irregular fighters during the conflict. He was so sure of their allegiance that in April 1815 he suggested that they be organized into the Nasiri regiment, a battalion commanded by Lieutenant Ross. Lieutenant Lawtie led this regiment, which subsequently evolved into the first King George's Own Gurkha Rifles. He told Ochterlony that he "had the greatest reason to be satisfied with their exertions" during the action at the Malaun fort. William Fraser and Lieutenant Frederick Young raised the Sir Moor battalion, which eventually became the second King Edward VII's Own Gurkha Rifles, in addition to the Ochterlony Gorkhali battalions. Another battalion, the Kumaon battalion, was also raised and eventually became the third Queen Alexandra's Own Gurkha Rifles. These men did not participate in the second campaign.
10. **Character fate**: Despite Nepal's defeat, Prime Minister Bhimsen Thapa maintained his position of authority with the help of Queen Regent Tripura Sundari. Other governing families, especially the Pandes, criticized Bhimsen Thapa's meek approach toward the British. Nonetheless, the prime minister was able to hold onto power during the minority of King Rajendra Bikram Shah (1816–1847) by keeping a sizable, modern army and exercising political control over the court. By placing members of his own family in positions of leadership, he was also able to keep the Pandes out of power. Following Queen Tripura Sundari's death in 1832, Bhimsen Thapa's power started to wane. After Brian Hodgson moved to Britain in 1833 and publicly supported Bhimsen Thapa's rivals, the king declared his desire to govern on his own in 1837, stripping the prime minister and his nephew of their military authority. Bhimsen Thapa was wrongfully accused of trying to poison the prince following the death of the queen's eldest son. Despite being exonerated, the Thapa family was in disarray. Bhimsen Thapa committed suicide in August 1839 after being re-incarcerated by Rana Jang Pande, the leader of the Pande dynasty, after he was appointed prime minister.
11. **David Ochterlony**: David Ochterlony, the first officer in the British East India Company to obtain the GCB, was thanked by both Houses of Parliament for his efforts. Additionally, Lord Moira restored him to his position as a resident of Delhi, where he lived in a manner befitting a

very high corporate official. However, Ochterlony lost favour after Lord Moira left India and Lord Amherst took over as Governor-General in 1823. When the Raja of Bharatpur passed away in 1825, Ochterlony backed his cousin Durjan Sal, who took the kingdom from the six-year-old successor. The British military was ready to march on Bharatpur when Durjan Sal refused to budge in response to Ochterlony demands that he leave the throne. However, the new Governor-General did not support him, and Amherst countermanded his instructions, which caused Ochterlony to retire, as Amherst had expected. The ill general was severely impacted by this occurrence and pass away on July 14, 1825, shortly after. The recruitment of Gorkhas into the Indian and British forces is Sir David Ochterlony greatest contribution, while a 165-foot-tall memorial was eventually built in Calcutta in his honor. Shortly after Ochterlony resignation.

12. **All about the Gorkha Regiment of the Indian Army:** When we hear the word "Gorkha," what comes to mind? Suddenly, a picture of "a few fearless warriors shouting Jai Mahakali Ayo Gorkhali while holding the holy weapon Kukhri" appears in your thoughts. You are therefore not alone if you feel that way. Gorkhas are renowned for their bravery and fearlessness. They are extremely talented fighters who have changed the outcome of numerous conflicts. Although they serve in numerous nations' armies, Gorkhas are primarily from India and Nepal. Gorkha soldiers have been employ by the Indian Army for a very long period. They have served in the armies of Maharaja Ranjit Singh and numerous other Indian monarchs. Their gallantry so impressed the British officers that the British that they were hired by the British in their regular army. The history of the Gorkha Regiment will be cover in this page, including battles and notable officers. Even now, Gorkhas serve in the Royal British Army. Let us learn more about the Indian Army's Gorkha Regiment.

- i. **Historical Background:** The Anglo-Nepalese War (1814–16) is when the Gorkha regiments' history begins. Because the Gorkha troops were so strong, the British East India Company decided to include them in their army. In 1815, the first Gorkha battalion was form. These regiments have since fought in innumerable historical conflicts, gaining a reputation for their ferocious devotion and outstanding fighting abilities. Gorkha soldiers took part in World War I as well. On the Western Front, Gorkha forces were crucial, particularly during the battles of Ypres and Neuve Chappelle. The Gorkha Regiment's soldiers received decorations such as the Victoria Cross, the highest award for valour during a conflict. Gorkha regiments made a substantial contribution and aided in the victory of the Allied Powers. From the

jungles of Burma to the deserts of North Africa, they battled in the strategic locations. Their valiant resistance changed the war in the Eastern theatre to the Japanese in Kohima and Imphal.

- ii. **Gorkha Regiment in Independent India:** The first King George V's Own Gorkha Rifles (the Malaun Regiment), the third Queen Alexandra's Own Gorkha Rifles, the fourth Prince of Wales's Own Gorkha Rifles, the fifth Royal Gorkha Rifles (Frontier Force), the eighth Gorkha Rifles, and the ninth Gorkha Rifles were among the six regiments of Gorkha soldiers that India receive after gaining independence. The Indian Army currently has seven regiments of Gorkha soldiers: the first, 3rd, 4th, 5th, 8th, 9th, and 11th battalions of the Gorkha Rifles. Gorkha troops have steadfastly protected India's frontiers from the freezing Siachen Glacier to the blazing Thar Desert. During the 1947 war, they played a pivotal part in recapturing Srinagar and their valiant defence of Kargil demonstrates their unshakeable spirit in 1999 and during the 1947 war.
13. **The Famous Soldiers and Officers of the Gorkha Regiment:** The bravery and valour of the Gorkha Regiment's officers and troops cannot be adequately capture in a single article. Here, we have highlighted a few well known Gorkha Regiment officers and soldiers.
- i. **Captain Gurbachan Singh Salaria:** Gurbachan Singh Salaria was a member of the Gorkha Rifles' first battalion. He received the Param Vir Chakra, making him the first NDA graduate to do so. For his valiant acts during a peacekeeping assignment in Katanga, Congo, he received the Param Vir Chakra. Despite being out number, Captain Salaria, the commander of the Gorkha battalion, fought valiantly to halt the enemy's advances.
 - ii. **Major Dhan Singh Thapa:** Carrying eight Gorkha rifles, Major Dhan Singh Thapa was a valiant Indian Army commander who was instrumental in the Sino-Indian War of 1962. He showed great heroism and valiantly defended his post at Rezang La in Ladakh during the Battle of Srijap. Chinese forces heavily fired on Major Dhan Singh Thapa and his men throughout this combat, and they were vastly outnumbered. He and his soldiers successfully repelled three consecutive Chinese attacks on the outpost in spite of intense shelling and heavy artillery fire. In appreciation of his exceptional leadership and bravery, Major Thapa received the Param Vir Chakra, India's highest military honor. The Indian Army dedicated a frontier outpost in his honor.

- iii. **Lieutenant Colonel Lalit Rai:** A distinguished Indian Army officer from the 11th Gorkha Rifles is Lieutenant Colonel Lalit Rai. During the Kargil War in 1999, he was renowned for his bravery. He was instrumental in the capture of vital Khalubar Top, leading his forces through hardship. Lieutenant Colonel Rai received the Maha Vir Chakra in recognition of his extraordinary bravery and leadership.
- iv. **Captain Manoj Pandey:** From the 11 Gorkha Rifles, Captain Manoj Pandey was a valiant member of the Indian Army. He is remembered for his valour in the Kargil War in 1999. He boldly rushed enemy positions in the perilous terrain, leading from the front. His teammates were motivated by Captain Pandey's unwavering determination and selflessness. For his extraordinary bravery and devotion to the country, he was posthumously awarded India's highest military honor, the Param Vir Chakra. His legacy endures as a testament to bravery and national pride.

14. **Quotes about the Gorkha Regiment:**

- i. *"If a man says he is not afraid of dying, he is either lying or is a Gorkha."*- Field Marshal Sam Manekshaw.
- ii. *"Bravest of the brave, most generous of generous, never had a country more faithful friends than you"*- Professor Sir Ralph Turner Mc.
- iii. *"The Gorkhas are the only people in the world who can laugh in the face of death."*- Field Marshal Lord Bramall, former Chief of Defence Staff.
- iv. *"The Gorkhas are small men, but they are very strong and very brave. They are like tigers."*-Jawaharlal Nehru, first Prime Minister of India.
- v. *"The Gorkhas have a reputation of being amongst the finest and most feared soldiers in the world. The Gorkha is the soldier who goes where others fear to tread."*-Queen Elizabeth II.
- vi. *"Hindustan has won no war without the sacrifices of Nepalese Soldiers, I salute those brave hearts who laid their lives for India"*-PM Narendra Modi (2014).

vii. *“It is better to fight Godzilla than A Gorkha Soldier.”- Unknown.*

15. **Gorkhas in the Assam Rifles: (Context):** The bravery and fearlessness of the Gorkhas greatly impressed the British during the Anglo-Nepal War of 1815–16. Under the leadership of the outstanding Gorkha General Amar Singh Thapa and his son Ranjore Singh Thapa, the Gorkhas achieved victory in Punjab's western battlefields. The second incident was the British attack on General Balbhadra's and his troops' mountain fortress of Kalanga, which was so unsuccessful that even when General Gillespie personally led the assault, the Gorkhas destroyed it and General Gillespie was killed by a Gorkha sniper from the fort. The third and last turning point occurred on February 17, 1815, when a tiny group of 200 Gorkhas, led by Lt. Fredric Young, ambushed a group of 2000 British irregulars with Kukhri. As a result, the entire irregular column fled, and Lt. Young was capture. According to legend, Lt. Young told the Gorkhas that he did not come all the way to run away when they asked him why he did not. The Gorkhas were impress by the young British officer's bravery, and the British believed that the Gorkhas were unbeatable on the battlefield. The British were so struck by the Gorkhas' devilish bravery that they coerced Gen. Amar Singh Thapa into accepting the recruitment of Gorkhas with respectable pay and benefits in the British Army even prior to the conclusion of the war and the signing of the Treaty of Sugauli on December 2, 1815. As a result, the first three British Gorkha battalions—the Sir moor Battalion, the Second Nasiri, and the First Nasiri—were raise in 1815.

- a. **The Recruitment:** Following peace with Nepal, the British turned their attention to the former Assam Province, which is now in the Northeast, where they were developing their infrastructure in order to plunder the area's abundant natural riches and grow their recently established tea estates. However, things were not going well in the region of Assam, and the British did not have it as easy as they believed. Tribal groups of Nagas, Mizos, and Kukis harassed British advance by raiding, looting, and retreating to the hills, sometimes carrying the skulls of British pioneers. The British recruited more Gorkhas to protect their people and build infrastructure in the Northeast as they were already enlisting Gorkhas and creating Gorkha battalions in mainland India. However, the army had to be region-specific, mostly assigned to protect their expansion into the North-eastern jungles. Accordingly, the British established the Assam Rifles in 1835, originally known as the Cachar Levy, using the labour of primarily Gorkhas recruited from Nepal together with Assamese, Kacharies, and Bodos. The force's mission was to protect the

Easter frontier from Brahmaputra to Cachar and conduct small-scale punitive expeditions against the raiding tribes of the hill regions. It was composed of roughly 80% Gorkhas, 10% Assamese, and 10% other tribes from the Northeast. According to British records, maintaining law and order was a constant task for the force in response to the constant acts of violence committed by tribal warriors who would raid British tea gardens, kill British officials, cross establish boundaries, or hunt down human heads in nearby villages. The British then began enlisting Gorkhas in the Assam Rifles in great numbers and urged them to relocate their families to isolated NE outposts at addition to their bravery; Gorkhas are hardworking and skilled at dairying and farming. As a result, they thrived in farming and dairy production while residing in those outposts and protecting the British borders. While the various battalions conducted the recruitment by sending their recruitment parties to Nepal, the Assam Rifles first recruited the majority of its personnel from the Gorkha region of Nepal. Eventually, the local recruiting offices took over the hiring process. Although the force and the mission remained the same, the name Cachar Levy was change to Assam Police by that point. Gorkhas in the Assam Police at the time served in France, Egypt, East Africa, Palestine, Mesopotamia, Gallipoli, North Persia, and the NW Frontier of India during World War I. Following World War I in 1917, the unit was renamed the Assam Rifles in honor of its exceptional performance on these battlefields, transforming it from a police force to a paramilitary force. As the military grew by 1917, recruitment was conducted through official army recruitment bureaus. Both the Gorkhas and the Assam Rifles grew significantly over time. Encouraged to live with their families, many Gorkhas chose to settle in and around their posts, which subsequently grew into sizable villages and towns, greatly increasing the number of Gorkhas in the Northeast. As a result, there are still a lot of Gorkhas in the Northeast today. Notably, Col. Sidhiman Rai, MC, a distinguished Gorkha officer from the Assam Regiment, was the first Indian Inspector General (since promoted to Director General) of the Assam Rifles.

16. **For what reason do the Gorkhas serve in the British Army?** The Gorkhas and the British first came into contact during the Gorkha War of 1814–1816, which ended not just in a standoff but also with a lasting sense of respect and regard for one another. Gorkhas were able to serve in the army of the East India Company, which later joined the British Army, thanks to the Peace Treaty that concluded the war. The Gorkhas have served all over the world since then. In

addition to serving with distinction in Hong Kong, Malaysia, Borneo, Cyprus, the Falklands, Kosovo, Sierra Leone, Iraq, and Afghanistan throughout the previous 50 years, over 200,000 served in the two World Wars. Additionally, they have distinguished themselves in combat in Hong Kong, Malaysia, Borneo, Cyprus, the Falklands, Kosovo, Sierra Leone, Iraq, and Afghanistan over the last half-century. The current number of Gurkhas serving is approximately 2,800, down from a peak of 112,000 troops during World War II. Although they mostly serve in the infantry, they also have a sizable number of engineers, logisticians, and signals specialists.

17. **British Indian Army (c 1857-1947)**: The Gurkha Regiments served in Burma, Afghanistan, Northeast India and the North-West Frontier of India, Malta (the Russo-Turkish War, 1877–78), Cyprus, Malaya, China (the Boxer Rebellion of 1900), and Tibet (Younghusband's Expedition of 1905) between the end of the Indian Rebellion in 1857 and the beginning of World War I. The British government in India was afraid of Hindu castes joining the army after the Indian Rebellion in 1857. Because they believed that Hindu castes were more receptive to Brahminical ideals and disapproved of Brahminical influence in the military, they refused to recruit tribes other than Gurungs and Magars for Gorkha troops and discouraged the inclusion of Thakuri and Khas groupings. In order to guarantee that at least 75% of new recruits were Gurungs and Magars, they also diplomatically pressured Prime Minister Bir Shamsheer Jang Bahadur Rana. The Gorkha regiments were renumbered from the first to the tenth and renamed the Gorkha Rifles between 1901 and 1906. The regiments, which is known as the Brigade of Gorkhas, expanded to 20 battalions within the ten regiments during this period. Over 200,000 Gorkhas served in the British Army during World War I (1914–1918), taking about 20,000 fatalities and winning nearly 2,000 heroism decorations. The Gorkha administrations increased the number of Gorkha battalions to 33 and placed Gorkha units at the British high command's disposal for duty on all fronts. Numerous Gorkha volunteers served in non-combatant capacities in labour battalions and the Army Bearer Corps, among other forces. Many of them also fought in Iraq, Palestine, France, and Turkey. They fought in Iraq, Persia, the Suez Canal, and Palestine against the Turkish onslaught, Gallipoli, and Salonika; they fought in France at the battles of Loos, Givenchy, and Neuve Chappelle; and they fought in Belgium at the battle of Ypres. Lawrence of Arabia served with one detachment. According to Indian Corps commander Lt. Gen. Sir James Willcocks, a battalion of the eighth Gorkhas "found its Valhalla" during the Battle of Loos (June–December 1915), fighting to the death and repeatedly throwing themselves against the weight of the German defences. The Gorkhas were between the first to

arrive and the last to go during the failed Gallipoli Campaign in 1915. The first/6th Gurkhas, who led the attack after landing at Cape Hellas during the first significant operation to conquer a Turkish high point, took a landmark that came to be known as “Gorkha Bluff”. The final goal of the campaign was to reach and maintain the crest line and gaze down on the straits, and they were the only troops to do this at Sari Bair. During the capture of Baghdad, the second/3rd Gurkha Rifles' second battalion participated. The Gorkhas returned to India after the war, and during the interwar years, they were mostly isolated from the subcontinent's urban conflicts and domestic unrest. Instead, they lived mostly on the borders and in the hills, where fiercely independent tribesmen caused trouble. The Gorkha regiments participated in the Third Afghan War in 1919 because of this. The regiments thereafter served as garrison forces protecting the North-West Frontier, primarily in Waziristan, where they took part in multiple wars. They interacted with the unruly and frequently openly antagonistic Pathan tribesmen and maintained harmony among the local population. There was a lot of political and civil upheaval on the North-West Frontier during this time, troops stationed at Razmak, Bannu, and Wana saw a lot of action. The Nepalese government offered to boost recruitment in order to increase the number of Gorkha battalions in British service to 35 after the British Expeditionary Force (BEF) evacuated Dunkirk in 1940. There were ten Gorkha regiments during World War II (1939–1945), each with two battalions, making 20 pre-war battalions. Eventually, this would increase to forty-three battalions. Third and fourth battalions were established for each of the 10 regiments in order to reach the increased number of battalions, and fifth battalions were raised for one GR, two GR, and nine GR. Ten training facilities for basic training and regimental records had to be established throughout India as a result of this development. To maintain calm in India and protect rear regions, five training battalions (14 GR, 29 GR, 38 GR, 56 GR, and 710 GR) were also raised, while additional units (25 GR and 26 GR) were raised as garrison battalions. During the war, 250,280 Gorkhas served in 40 battalions, and eight Nepalese Army battalions, parachute, training, garrison, and porter units in nearly every theatre. Many Gorkha men were also recruited for non-Gurkha units and other specialized jobs like para troops, signals, engineers, and military police. Gorkhas fought against the Japanese in the jungles of Burma, northeast India, and Singapore, as well as in Syria, North Africa, Italy, and Greece, in addition to maintaining peace in India. They accomplished this with distinction, suffering almost 32,000 casualties across all theatres and receiving 2,734 honors for courage.

18. **British Indian Army Gorkha military rank system:** The British Indian Army's Gorkha ranks were based on the same structure as the rest of the Indian Army at the time. There were three different levels, just like in the British Army: commissioned officers, non-commissioned officers, and private soldiers. The "Viceroy's Commission" held by Gorkha commissioned officers in Gorkha regiments was different from the King's or Queen's Commission held by British officers in a Gorkha regiment. Technically, every Gorkha with a commission, whatever of rank, was subordinate to any British commander.

19. **Rank equivalents in modern Indian and British Armies:**

a. **Viceroy Commissioned Officers (VCOs) up to 1947 and Junior Commissioned Officers (JCOs) from 1947:**

- i. Subedar Major/no equivalent.
- ii. Subedar/no equivalent.
- iii. Jemadar (now Naik Subedar)/no equivalent.

b. **Warrant officers:**

- i. Regimental Havildar Major/Warrant Officer Class 1
- ii. Company Havildar Major/Warrant Officer Class 2

c. **Non-commissioned officers:**

- i. Company Quartermaster Havildar/Colour Sergeant.
- ii. Havildar/Sergeant.
- iii. Naik/Corporal.
- iv. Lance Naik/Lance Corporal

d. **Private soldiers:**

- i. **Rifleman-**Under this system, Gorkha officers received the Viceroy's Commission, while British Army officers earned the Queen's or King's Commissions. The King's (later Queen's) Gorkha Commission was given to Gurkha officers in regiments that joined the British Army following Indian independence in 1947. These officers were referred to as King's/Queen's Gorkha

Officers (KGO/QGO). British regiment troops could not be commanded by Gorkha officers. In 2007, the QGO Commission was disband While the Subedar major was the Commanding Officer's counsellor on the men and their welfare, Jemadar and Subedar were junior to all British officers and typically held the positions of platoon commander and company 2IC. However, they were subordinate to all British officers, and the Subedar major advised the Commanding Officer on the men's well-being. Gorkhas were unable to advance for a long time, with the exception of the honorary lieutenancy or captaincy that was (very rarely) awarded to a Gurkha upon retirement. In the Indian Army after 1947, the equivalent ranks were (and still are) called Junior Commissioned Officers (JCOs). They continued to utilize the same rank titles as the British Indian Army: Subedar, Subedar Major, and Jemadar (later Naib Subedar). Gorkhas cannot apply for a commission without having served in the ranks, but any British subject may in theory do so. Before his regiment would consider granting him a commission, a Gorkha soldier was expected to advance through the ranks and demonstrate his abilities. Gorkhas were placed on an equal footing with British officers once they were granted King's Indian Commissions in the 1920s and then full King's or Queen's Commissions. Prior to the Second World War, this was uncommon. Gorkha officers and short service officers who were commission at the Royal Military Academy Sandhurst frequently hold posts up to Major. According to theory, there is nothing stopping at least two Gorkhas from being elevated to lieutenant colonel. With the exception of the three Viceroy Commission ranks between Warrant Officer 1 and Second Lieutenant (Jemadar, Subedar, and Subedar major), which persisted despite having distinct rank titles Lieutenant (Queens Gurkha Officer), Captain (QGO), and Major (QGO), the Brigade of Gorkhas (a division of the British Army) was established after 1948 and adopted the standard British Army rank structure and nomenclature. Gorkha soldiers are now commission as Late Entry Officers (as mentioned above) after the QGO commission was abolish in 2007.

- e. **Regiments of the Gorkha Rifles (c. 1815–1947):** Memorial of 10th Princess Mary's Own Gorkha Rifles, Winchester Cathedral, Hampshire Princess Mary's Own.

- i. 1st King George V's Own Gorkha Rifles (The Malaun Regiment) (raised 1815, allocated to Indian Army at independence in 1947).
 - ii. 2nd King Edward VII's Own Gorkha Rifles (The Sir moor Rifles) (raised 1815, allocated to British Army in 1948).
 - iii. 3rd Queen Alexandra's Own Gorkha Rifles (raised 1815, allocated to Indian Army at independence in 1947).
 - iv. 4th Prince of Wales's Own Gorkha Rifles (raised 1857, allocated to Indian Army at independence in 1947).
 - v. 5th Royal Gorkha Rifles (Frontier Force) (raised 1858, allocated to Indian Army at independence in 1947).
 - vi. 6th Gorkha Rifles, renamed 6th Queen Elizabeth's Own Gorkha Rifles in 1959 (raised 1817, allocated to British Army in 1948).
 - vii. 7th Gorkha Rifles, renamed 7th Duke of Edinburgh's Own Gorkha Rifles in 1959 (raised 1902, allocated to British Army in 1948).
 - viii. 8th Gorkha Rifles (raised 1824, allocated to Indian Army at independence in 1947).
 - ix. 9th Gorkha Rifles (raised 1817, allocated to Indian Army at independence in 1947).
 - x. 10th Princess Mary's Own Gorkha Rifles (raised 1890, allocated to British Army in 1948).
 - xi. 11th Gorkha Rifles (1918–1922; raised again by India – 11 Gorkha Rifles – following independence in 1947).
 - xii. 25th Gorkha Rifles (1942–1946).
 - xiii. 26th Gorkha Rifles (1943–1946).
 - xiv. 29th Gorkha Rifles (1943–1946).
 - xv. 42nd Gorkha Rifles (raised 1817 as the Cuttack Legion, renamed 6^t Gurkha Rifles in 1903).
 - xvi. 44th Gorkha Rifles (raised 1824 as the 16th (Sylhet) Local Battalion, renamed 8th Gurkha Rifles in 1903).
- f. **Second World War training battalions:**
- i. 14th Gorkha Rifles Training Battalion.

- ii. 29th Gorkha Rifles Training Battalion.
- iii. 38th Gorkha Rifles Training Battalion.
- iv. 56th Gorkha Rifles Training Battalion.
- v. 710th Gorkha Rifles Training Battalion.

20. **Post-Independence (1947–present):** Following Indian independence and the division of India, the British Army and the newly independent Indian Army divided the original ten Gorkha regiments, which comprised the 20 pre-war battalions, according to the Tripartite Agreement signed by the governments of the United Kingdom, India, and Nepal. Four Gorkha regiments (eight battalions) were transferred to the British Army, while six regiments (12 battalions) were transferred to the Indian Army after independence. Most Gorkhas who were offered the option of serving in the Indian Army or the British Army chose the latter, much to the dismay of many of their British officers. The rationale seems to have been the practical one that the Indian Army's Gorkha regiments would carry on with their current duties in well-known areas and under well-established terms and conditions. Indian officers were substituted for British officers, which was the only significant alteration. The four regiments chosen for British service, on the other hand, faced an uncertain future, first in Malaya, a place where very few Gorkhas had served before. In British service, the four regiments (eight battalions) were later consolidated into a single regiment consisting of two battalions. The Indian units have grown beyond the twelve battalions that were established prior to independence. Ensuring that Gorkhas serving under the Crown would get compensation comparable to that of those serving in the nascent Indian Army was the main goal of the Tripartite Agreement. The standard rate of pay in Britain was far higher than this. The cost of living and location allowances during a Gorkha's real service tenure make up the difference, but the pension that is due to him upon his return to Nepal is far less than what his British peers would receive. At first, it was unclear if Gorkhas would be recruited into the Indian and British military services when Nepal's monarchy was abolished in 2008. "Recruiting as mercenaries is degrading to the Nepalese people and will be banned," said a spokesperson for the Communist Party of Nepal (Maoist) (later the Communist Party of Nepal (Maoist Centre)), which was expected to play a key role in the new secular republic. Nonetheless, Gorkha is still hiring for the Foreign Service as of 2023.

21. **British Army (Gorkhas):** Four Gorkha regiments were transferred to the British Army on 1 January 1948:

- i. 2nd King Edward VII's Own Gorkha Rifles (The Sir moor Rifles)
- ii. 6th Queen Elizabeth's Own Gorkha Rifles
- iii. 7th Duke of Edinburgh's Own Gorkha Rifles
- iv. 10th Princess Mary's Own Gorkha Rifles

They were first station in Malaya and constituted the Brigade of Gorkhas. A number of other Gorkha regiments were also there, such as the 36th Engineer Regiment's 69th and 70th Gurkha Field Squadrons. Since then, British Gorkhas have participated in the Falklands War, the conflict with Indonesia in Borneo, and several peacekeeping assignments in East Timor, Sierra Leone, Bosnia, and Kosovo.

22. Major Gorkha Formations:

- i. 43rdIndependent Gorkha Infantry Brigade (Italy, circa 1943).
- ii. 26thGorkha Brigade (Hong Kong, 1948–1950).
- iii. 17thGorkha Division (Malaya, 1952–1970).
- iv. 51stInfantry Brigade (Hong Kong disbanded 1976).
- v. 48thGorkha Infantry Brigade (Hong Kong, 1957–1976; renamed Gurkha Field Force 1976–1997; returned to old title 1987 – c. 1992).

23. As of August 2021, the Brigade of Gorkhas in the British Army has the following units:

- i. 1stBattalion, The Royal Gorkha Rifles (1RGR).
- ii. 2ndBattalion, The Royal Gorkha Rifles (2RGR).
- iii. 3rdBattalion, The Royal Gorkha Rifles (3RGR).
- iv. Gurkha Allied Rapid Reaction Corps Support Battalion

24. Queen in Gorkha Signals , which includes:

- i. 250 Gorkha Signal Squadron, 30 Signal Regiment.
- ii. 246Gorkha Signal Squadron, 2Signal Regiment.
- iii. 247 Gorkha Signal Squadron, 16 Signal Regiment.
- iv. 248 Gorkha Signal Squadron, 22 Signal Regiment.
- v. 249Gorkha Signal Squadron, third (UK) Division Signal Regiment.
- vi. 10thQueen's Own Gorkha Logistic Regiment RLC.

25. Queen in Gorkha Engineers, which includes:

- i. 69th Gorkha Field Squadron, 36 Engineer Regiment.
- ii. 70th Gorkha Field Squadron, 36 Engineer Regiment.
- iii. Gorkha Staff and Personnel Support Company.
- iv. Band of the Brigade of Gorkhas.
- v. Gorkha Company (Sittang), Royal Military Academy Sandhurst.
- vi. Gorkha Wing (Mandalay), Infantry Battle School.
- vii. Gorkha Company (Tavoletto), Land Warfare Centre.

Among the aforementioned units are the Brigade of Gorkhas' own chefs. Gurkhas served several tours of duty in the War in Afghanistan and were part of the forces that retook the Falklands in 1982. Gorkhas have been part of the British Army for almost 200 years.

- a. "Better to die than be a coward" is the motto of the world-famous Nepalese Gorkha soldiers who are an integral part of the British Army.
- b. Gorkha soldiers carry their traditional weapon - an 18-inch long curved knife known as the kukhri, there is a well-known saying that, once a kukhri is taken out from the cover in the battle, it had to "taste blood" - if not, its owner had to cut himself before returning it to its sheath.
- c. The potential of the Gorkha warriors was first realised by the British at the height of their empire building in the last century.
- d. The Victorians identified them as a "martial race", perceiving in them particularly masculine qualities of toughness.
- e. After suffering heavy casualties in the invasion of Nepal, the British East India Company signed a hasty peace deal in 1815, which also allowed it to recruit from the ranks of the former enemy.
- f. Following the partition of India in 1947, an agreement between Nepal, India and Britain meant four Gorkha regiments from the Indian army were transfer to the British Army, eventually becoming the Gorkha Brigade.
- g. Since then, the Gorkhas have loyally fought for the British all over the world, receiving 13 Victoria Crosses between them.
- h. More than 200,000 fought in the two world wars, and in the past 50 years, they have served in Hong Kong, Malaysia, Borneo, Cyprus, the Falklands, Kosovo and now in Iraq and Afghanistan.
- i. They serve in a variety of roles, mainly in the infantry but with significant numbers of engineers, logisticians and signals specialists.
- j. The name "Gorkha" comes from the hill town of Gorkha from which the Nepalese kingdom had expanded.

- k. Four ethnic communities of Gorkha such as the Gurungs and the Magars from central Nepal and the Rai and Limbus from the eastern side of Nepal, who live in villages of impoverished hill farmers, have always dominated the ranks.
- l. In British Army the customs, religion and beliefs of the Gorkha people such as Dashain, Deepawali are celebrated and even the goats and buffaloes are sacrifice.
- m. Actor Joanna Lumley has been the public face of the campaign on behalf of the Gurkhas.
- n. More than 43, 000 Gorkhas lost their lives during the WW II.
- o. The Gurkhas are now base at Shorncliffe near Folkestone, Kent – but still denied of British citizenship.
- p. The soldiers are young men living in the hills of Nepal –and around 28,000 youths tackling the selection procedure for just over 200 places each year.
- q. The selection process of the British Army are one of the toughest in the world.
- r. Young soldiers have to run uphill for 40 minutes carrying a wicker basket on their back filled with rocks weighing 70lbs.
- s. Prince Harry has also lived with a Gorkha battalion in Afghanistan for around 10 weeks and noticed that there is a cultural affinity between Gurkhas and the Afghan people, which is beneficial to the British Army.
- t. Historian Tony Gould said Gorkhas have brought an excellent combination of qualities from a military point of view, he further said that, “They are tough, brave, durable and discipline.
- u. Historically, Gorkhas who had served in the Army - a maximum of 30 years, and a minimum of 15years to secure a pension - were discharge back to Nepal.

26. **Pension battle:**

- i. All retired Gorkhas won the right to live in the UK, following a high-profile campaign led by actor Joanna Lumley, whose father served with the 6th Gorkha Rifles.
- ii. 2. Gorkha veterans continue to fight for pensions on par with those who served along side them.
- iii. Soldiers won a partial victory when pension rules were changein2007.They paythesame amount of money to both pensioners and active duty soldiers in the UK, but the UK's Gorkha Welfare Associationes timates that around 25,000 soldiers returned to the army before 1 July 1997. He said he was being deny the opportunity to benefit from the UK pension system. This was because the government illegally paid the military one-third of the income of soldiers stationed in the UK.

iv. A High Court test case in January 2010 ruled in favour of the Ministry of Defence, which argued the pension cut-off date was "justified and proportionate", but the decision has since been challenge by the Gorkhas, who have taken their battle to the Court of Appeal.

27. Indian Army Gorkhas:

Upon independence in 1947, six of the original ten Gorkha regiments remained with the Indian Army. These regiments were:

- i. 1st King George V's Own Gorkha Rifles (The Malaun Regiment).
- ii. 3rd Queen Alexandra's Own Gorkha Rifles.
- iii. 4th Prince of Wales's Own Gorkha Rifles.
- iv. 5th Royal Gorkha Rifles (Frontier Force).
- v. 8th Gorkha Rifles.
- vi. 9th Gorkha Rifles.

Additionally, a further regiment, 11 Gorkha Rifles, was raise. In 1949, the spelling was change from "Gurkha" to the original "Gorkha". All royal titles were drop when India became a republic in 1950.

Since partition, the Gurkha regiments that were transfer to the Indian Army have established themselves as a permanent and vital part of the newly independent Indian Army. Indeed, while Britain has reduced its Gurkha contingent, India has continued to recruit Gorkhas of Nepal into Gorkha regiments in large numbers, as well as Indian Gorkhas. In 2009, the Indian Army had a Gorkha contingent that numbered around 42,000 men in 46 battalions, spread across seven regiments.

Although their deployment was, still govern by the 1947 Tripartite Agreement, in the post-1947 conflicts India has fought in, Gorkhas have served in almost all of them, including the wars with Pakistan in 1947, 1965, 1971 and 1999 and against China in 1962. They have also been use in peacekeeping operations around the world. They have also served in Sri Lanka conducting operations against the Tamil Tigers.

28. Singapore Gorkha Contingent:

A trooper of the Gorkha Contingent of the Singapore Police Force gives directions to a civilian. The Gorkha Contingent (GC) of the Singapore Police Force was form in 9 April 1949 from selected ex-

British Army Gorkhas. It is an integral part of the police force and was raised to replace a Sikh unit that had existed prior to the Japanese occupation during the Second World War. The GC is a well-trained, dedicated and disciplined organization whose primary role is to control riots. In times of crisis, it can be used as a counterattack force. During the turbulent years before and after independence, the Attorney General was repeatedly spared the outbreak of civil war. The Gorkhas were famous for their courage, self-control, and professionalism, which earned them the respect of society.

29. Brunei Gorkha Reserve Unit:

The Gorkha Reserve Unit (GRU) is a special guard and elite shock-troop force in the Sultanate of Brunei. The Brunei Reserve Unit employs about 500 Gorkhas. The majority are veterans of the British Army and the Singaporean Police, who have joined the GRU as a second career.

30. Indian Special Frontier Force: The Special Frontier Force (SFF) is an Indian paramilitary organization consisting of Tibetan refugees, Nepali Gorkhas, and other ethnic groups from mountainous areas. The SFF is tasked with conducting covert actions against China in the event of another Sino-Indian war. The SFF was originally intended to exclusively consist of Tibetan refugees living in India, however, the SFF began recruiting Nepali Gorkhas and hill tribesmen in 1965 to make up for a declining recruitment rate among Tibetans. It is believed there are around 700 Gorkhas serving in the SFF.

31. Victoria Cross recipients:

The 26 Victoria Crosses (VC) were awarded to soldiers from the Gorkha regiments. The first was awarded in 1858 and the last in 1965. Thirteen of the recipients have been British officers serving with Gorkha regiments. Since 1915, the majority have been awarded to Gorkhas serving in the ranks as private soldiers or NCOs. Since Indian independence in 1947, Gorkhas serving in the Indian Army have been awarded three Param Vir Chakras, which are equivalent to the Victoria Cross.

Two George Cross (GC) medals have been awarded to Gorkha soldiers for acts of bravery. The George Cross (GC) is the highest award bestowed by the British government for non-operational gallantry or gallantry not in the presence of an enemy. In the UK honours system, the George Cross is equal in stature to the Victoria Cross. This has been the case since the introduction of the George Cross in 1940.

32. Treatment of Gurkhas in the United Kingdom:

Nick Clegg attended Maids tone wearing a Gorkha veteran's Gorkha cap to celebrate the success of the 2009 United Right to Life campaign. His treatment of Gorkhas and their families became a controversial topic in 2009. In Britain, it became widely known that the Gorkhas received lower pensions than their British compatriots did. The nationality of the Gorkhas and their families was also controversial. It is claim that some Nepalese ex-army families have been refuse residence permits and forced to leave the UK. On 8 March 2007, the British government announced that all Gorkhas who registered after 1 July 1997 would receive a pension equal to that of Gorkhas in the UK. In addition, Gorkhas can only be transfer to other army units after five years of service, and women can join the British Army in line with policy, although they are not part of the frontline. The Act also guaranteed retired Gorkhas and their families the right to reside in Britain. Despite the changes, many Gorkhas who had not served long enough to entitle them to a pension faced hardship on their return to Nepal, and some critics derided the government's decision to only award the new pension and citizenship entitlement to those joining after 1 July 1997, claiming that this left many ex-Gurkha servicemen still facing a financially uncertain retirement. An advocacy group, Gorkha Justice Campaign, joined the debate in support of the Gorkhas. In a landmark ruling on 30 September 2008, Mr Justice Blake in the High Court in London decided that the Home Secretary's policy allowing Gorkhas who left the Army before 1997 to apply for settlement in the United Kingdom was irrationally restrictive in its criteria, and overturn it. He upheld the claim of six Gorkha soldiers for the right to settle in Britain at the end of their service, reciting the Military Covenant and observing that granting them residence in Britain "would, in my judgment, be a vindication and an enhancement of this covenant". In response to the decision of the High Court, the Home Office said it would review all cases that were affect by it. On April 29, 2009, a motion introduced by the Liberal Democratic Partyt ogrant equal housing rights to all Gorkha residents was pass in the House of Commons by avoteof 267 to 246. This was the government's only first-day defeat since 1978. Liberal Democrat leader Nick Clegg declared: "This is an immense victory... for the rights of the Gorkha people who have been waiting for justice, and for the people. "Congress, this is a victory for common sense,"hesaid, adding that "the kind of thing people want in this country. "On Home Secretary Jacqui Smith declared on May 21, 2009, that all Gorkha veterans who served for at least four years and resigned prior to 1997 would be permitted to settle in the UK. "This is the welcome we have always longed to give," said actor Joanna Lumley, daughter of Gurkha corps Major James Lumley, who had advocated for the rights of the Gurkhas and brought attention to their treatment. The Gorkha Welfare Trust is a non-profit organization that helps Gurkha veterans who are experiencing poverty and misery. Gorkha Square in Fleet, Hampshire, which houses the Fleet war memorial, is name after the

Gorkhas. On June 9, 2015, members of the royal family attended a celebration known as the Gorkha 200, which honours Gurkha culture and military service and marks the bicentennial of the Gurkha Welfare Trust.

33. **Settlement rights:** The "debt of honor" owed to Gurkhas discharged before to 1997 was recognized in a 2008 UK High Court ruling in the test case of R. (on the application of Limbu) v. Secretary of State for the Home Department [2008] EWHC 2261 (Admin). It was decided that the Home Secretary's policy, which permitted veterans to apply based on a restricted set of criteria (such a connection to the United Kingdom), was excessively restrictive. The Court concluded that there had been a "historic injustice" to the Gurkhas and that the policy was unreasonable for ignoring things like service duration or exceptionally good behaviour.
34. **Anglo-Nepalese War, 1815:** The Gorkhali army of the Kingdom of Nepal (modern-day Nepal) and the British forces of the East India Company (EIC, modern-day India) fought each other in the Anglo-Nepalese War (1 November 1814–4 March 1816), sometimes referred to as the Gorkha War. The Indian Subcontinent's rugged north was the target of both sides' ambitious expansion intentions. The Sugauli Treaty, which was sign in 1816 and gave the EIC some of the Nepalese-controlled territory, put a stop to the war. The East India Company against the Kingdom of Gorkha led the British war effort. Amar Singh Thapa's family and the Thapa dynasty spearheaded the majority of the Kingdom of Gorkha's military effort.
 - a. **Background:** The British East India Company engaged in extensive trading with Nepal around the middle of the eighteenth century. Considered a centre of luxury, Nepal provided the Company with goods including gold, oil seeds, rice, butter, lumber, and dyes. When the Gorkhas rose to prominence and authority in Nepal in 1767, British worries about this alliance intensified. The relationship between British India and Nepal began to deteriorate in 1768 when the Gorkhas took control of the Kathmandu Valley and established themselves as the country's dominant force. To have more control over the area, the Company founded a British Residency in Kathmandu in 1801. However, the prospect of a partnership between Nepal and the Sikhs in northern India began to worry the British as 1814 drew near. The Company thought that Nepal would cease to be a threat if it were driven out of its Western territories, the "Terai" region. This is what the British set out to achieve in 1814, along with the intention of setting up a second Residency in Kathmandu to closely monitor the country. British troops in Nepal briefly departed in May 1814 in order to avoid the malaria season. Company officials were kill

when Nepali forces attempted to regain control. Bengal's governor general, Warren Hastings, formally declared war on Nepal in 1814. Then, in September 1814, about 16,000 men were sent to conquer Nepal. The Anglo-Nepalese War was thus declared over by the Treaty of Sugauli (1816). Additional details: East India Company, Sino-Nepalese War, and Nepal's unification. The Gorkha King Prithvi Narayan Shah invaded the Kathmandu Valley, which included the Malla confederacy's capital, marking the start of Nepal's Shah Era. Up until that point, Nepal has solely been used to refer to the Kathmandu Valley. When the Confederacy asked the East India Company for assistance, Captain Kinlock launched a poorly planned and equipped expedition of 2,500 people in 1767. The Gorkhali army quickly defeated those who had not perished from desperation or malaria because of the disastrous expedition. The ineffective British army gave the Gorkhali weapons and gave the Gorkhas confidence, which may have led them to misjudge their rivals in subsequent conflicts, because of Prithvi Narayan Shah's conquest and occupation of the Kathmandu Valley, which started with the Battle of Kirtipur, his kingdom's capital was moved from Gorkha to Kathmandu, and he and his descendants established the empire that is today known as Nepal. Furthermore, the invasion of the affluent Kathmandu Valley gave the Gorkha force financial backing to advance its regional military aspirations. However, Chinese engagement was prompted to the north by violent attacks into Tibet over a long-standing dispute over commerce and control of the mountain routes. A force headed by the Chinese Qianlong Emperor drove the Nepalese out of Tibet in 1792, bringing them within 5 kilometres (3.1 miles) of Kathmandu, their capital. The younger son of Prithvi Narayan, Acting Regent Bahadur Shah, made a request for assistance from the British Governor-General of India. The Governor-General dispatched Captain Kirkpatrick as a mediator rather than troops because he was worried about a conflict with the Chinese. However, the conflict with China was over before he got there. The Tibet issue had delayed a planned attack on the Garhwali Kingdom, but Pradyuman Shah, the Raja of Garhwal, had also been vanquished by 1803. In January 1804, he was killed in battle, and his entire territory was annexed. General Amar Singh Thapa seized and besieged regions farther to the west, including the strongest mountain stronghold in Himachal Pradesh, Kangra, in the south. However, in 1809, Punjab's ruler, Maharaja Ranjit Singh, drove the Nepali army beyond the Sutlej River.

- b. **Causes**: The British had been extending their sphere of influence in the years preceding the conflict. The British East India Company had solidified its position in India from its primary bases of Calcutta, Madras, and Bombay, while the Nepalese had been growing their kingdom into Sikkim to the east, the Kumaon and Garhwal to the west, and Awadh to the south. In India, opposition to this British expansion had already resulted in three Anglo-Maratha wars. In the Punjab, Ranjit Singh and the Sikh Empire had their own goals.
- c. **Territorial Conflict**: One of the main causes of the Anglo-Nepalese War is territorial strife. First, the Company's conceptions of space and territoriality ran counter to Nepal's ideas about boundaries and borderlands. Conflicts over borderlands were a major factor in the conflict between Nepal and British India prior to 1814. Borderlands are "zones of contact for the management, separation, and negotiation of difference." The Himalayas have always been a place of complex agrarian entitlements and political elasticity. Nepal's borders were therefore still open. Nepal had "an unbounded space" as opposed to set territorial limits, which allowed for diverse trade and population migrations. Landholding patterns, tribute and taxation claims, and environmental factors all contributed to the periodic administrative changes along Nepal's boundaries. Control of the Anglo-Gorkha borderlands, which are Nepal's borders with British India, therefore fluctuated regularly between several agents. The British began to have serious concerns about these frontiers in the eighteenth century. Because the British considered borders unchangeable and immovable, the Company saw Nepal's movable borders as incursions into British territory. The Company started conducting surveys and creating maps because of territorial concerns. The goal of these endeavours was to make Nepal's political and administrative borders "more legible for colonial rule." The Revenue Surveys then created these maps in the nineteenth century, and the Company used them as a method to partition the land into set, non-overlapping areas. Thus, clashing notions of boundaries and spatiality were crucial in the run-up to the Anglo-Nepalese War in 1814, when territorial conflicts reached their peak. The Treaty of Sugauli contents demonstrate how disputes over territorial claims contributed to the outbreak of the conflict. According to Article 2, "The Raja of Nepal acknowledges the right of the Honourable Company to the sovereignty of those lands and renounces all claim to the lands which were the subject of discussion between the two States prior to the war." One

example of how territorial concern fuelled the war is the British soldiers' emphasis on land and territoriality throughout the various sections of this treaty. Following the listing of five extremely specific territorial areas, Article 3 further declares, "The Raja of Nepal hereby cedes to the Honourable the East India Company in perpetuity all the under-mentioned territories." For instance, the Treaty specifies that "hills eastward of the River Mitchel including the fort and lands of Nagree and the Pass of Nagarcote leading from Morung into the hills" be among these ceded properties. The Company's extremely rigid views of borders and borderlands are once again demonstrate by these high degrees of specificity. Nepal lost around one-third of its territory because of the Anglo-Nepalese War and the treaty that followed. Because of the Company's intense worries about Nepal's shifting borders in the years and decades prior, territorial disputes served as a catalyst for conflict. The British East India Company's purchase of the Nawab of Awadh's territories placed Gorakhpur in close proximity to Palpa, the last autonomous town in the Nepalese heartlands and the raja (king). Originally, two distinct countries, Palpa and Butwal were merge under a single independent Rajput monarch who added Butwal to his inherited Palpa lands after defeating it. Even though Butwal's estates were seized and annexed, they were nevertheless held in fief, or paid an annual payment, first to Awadh and then to the British by transfer. The hill nation of Palpa was subjugate and incorporated into Nepal around the end of the 18th century, during the reign of Rani Rajendra Laxmi. After retreating to Butwal, the raja was persuaded to travel to Kathmandu under false pretences of redress, where he was executed and the Nepalese took control of his Butwal lands. Serious boundary disputes arose between the two countries after Bhimsen Thapa, the prime minister of Nepal from 1806 to 1837, appointed his own father as governor of Palpa. The direct cause of the Anglo-Nepalese conflict in 1814 was the Nepalese occupation of the Terai of Butwal, which lasted from 1804 to 1812 while the British protected it. When the ambitious Earl of Moira took over as Governor-General in October 1813, his first action was to re-examine the boundary dispute between Nepal and the British East India Company. There was no clear border between the British and the Nepalese, which led to these conflicts. The British had no knowledge of the country or its resources, and despite their superior technology, they were convinced that the mountainous terrain they would have to traverse would be as perplexing to them as it had been to the numerous succeeding Mahomedan rulers. As a

result, a battle with the former was unlikely to succeed. The Governor-General imposed a border commission on Nepal, but it was unable to resolve the issue. The Nepali commissioners informed the British that unless Britain granted Nepal all of the British provinces north of the Ganges River, there could be no true peace between the two nations, therefore there was no value in talking about a few square miles of territory. The significance of that, he noted. This indicates that the river created the border between the two nations "as heaven clearly intended," but Nepali historian Baburam Acharya disagrees, asserting that the British were responsible for the border dispute because they sought to annex Nepal's mountainous areas. At the border, Major Bradshaw, speaking for the British, insulted Raj Guru Ranganath Poudyal and Kazi Dalabhanjan Pande, speaking for the Nepalese, in an attempt to incite war against Nepal following the border's demarcation. Meanwhile, the British discovered that the Nepalese were getting ready for war; they had been building up huge saltpetre stores for a while, buying and making weapons, and arranging and training their soldiers under some European deserters in this service, following the example of the sepoy battalions of East India's companies. The British believed their power in the area and their precarious lines of communication between Calcutta and the northwest were in jeopardy because of the Nepalese raids into the flatlands of the Terai, a highly valued strip of fertile land separating the Nepalese hill country from India. Confrontation between the two powers was "necessary and unavoidable" because there was no defined border. Nepal was officially declared to be at war 1 November 1814.

- d. **Economic Interests:** Another important factor contributing to the Anglo-Nepalese War is economic interests. Initially, the British aimed to use Kathmandu and eastern Nepal as part of the trans-Himalayan trading routes. These routes would provide British-made commodities access to unexplored markets in China and Tibet. Therefore, the Company focused on trading between Tibet and British territories in Bengal in the late eighteenth century. In order to advance these trade interests and build business ties with Nepal, Bhutan, and eventually Tibet, trade missions were conducted under Warren Hastings' direction. Chinese silks, wool, dyestuffs, and other enticing goods were sourced from Tibet. However, the British saw Nepal's advance into the Terai areas and the Gorkha's capture of the Kathmandu Valley in the latter half of the eighteenth century as a danger to the Company's trading objectives. Thus, British economic interests mostly caused the

Anglo-Nepalese War. Britain's ceding of Nepali areas that encompassed these lucrative trade routes in the Treaty of Sugauli serves as an example of these commercial goals. The British had been trying to convince the Nepalese authorities to let them trade through Nepal to reach legendary Tibet. The Nepalese Durbar remained unmoved by a string of delegations led by William Kirkpatrick (1792), Maulvi Abdul Qader (1795), and then William O. Knox (1801). The Nepalese proverb "With the merchants come the musket and with the Bible comes the bayonet" encapsulates the opposition to opening the nation to Europeans. Lord Hastings had no qualms about taking advantage of any business prospects that might arise from having access to the Himalayan region. Given that the East India Company was currently experiencing a cash-flow problem, he was aware that they would appease his bosses and quell his detractors. To cover overhead, pensions, and dividends, it required a sizable amount of money in Britain; nevertheless, there were issues sending the required assets from India. The business had historically purchased Indian products and resold it in London, but this was no longer financially viable. Cotton products were India's main export, but as domestic textiles gained traction in the British market, demand for these products was dropping. As a result, the business had to transfer its assets in a different, more costly, and convoluted manner. Since all tea at this time originated from China and wasn't available in India until the 1840s, it had to send its Indian textiles to Canton, sell them on the Chinese market, use the money it made to buy tea, and then sail the tea to Britain for sale. The company's directors were quickly intrigued when Hastings presented them with a different method of shipping precious and rare items that could be comfortably and easily deliver straight from India to London. The finest quality wool, an incredibly delicate and resilient animal down, is the raw material used to create Kashmir's renowned shawls. Only in specific regions of western Tibet can one find scarf-wool goats, which are the only animals that have this feather. They would not breed elsewhere. All of this explains why Nepal's 1816 treaty required her to give up her far western territories. Hastings thought that British merchants would have direct access to wool-growing regions thanks to this province, which was partially return to its original rulers after being partially seize by the Company. Similarly, on August 24, 1814, David Ochterlony, who was an agent in Ludhiana at the time, described Dehra Dun as a "potentially thriving entrepot for Trans-Himalayan trade." He considered annexing Garhwal for the security of economic communications with the nation that

- produces the shawl wool, rather than so much for making money. The British must soon know the fact that Kumaon offered improved facilities for trade with Tibet. As a result, one of their strategic goals was to acquire these two regions.
- e. **Security Concerns**: It is improbable that the Company would have started such a costly and difficult war without a desire to "eliminate one of the few remaining threats to British dominance in northern India," even though territoriality was the direct source of the conflicts between Nepal and the British. Thus, the war was also sparked by the Company's security worries. Nepal's territory was situated just north of Bengal, the centre of British governance, in the early nineteenth century, prior to the Anglo-Nepalese War. The British were in danger because of this. The Company was concerned that anti-British sentiment among the Nepalese could lead to either an attack on Bengal that would make it more difficult for the British to communicate with North India or the formation of an anti-British alliance by Indian states. The Gorkhas' spectacular victories of the Kathmandu Valley also gave the British an inflated perception of Nepal's power, which helped them see the country as a security danger. The Gorkhas' steadfast resistance to British coercion since the 1760s exacerbated British security worries. British security concerns are reflected in the Treaty of Sugauli. "The Raja of Nepal renounces for himself, his heirs, and successors, any claim to or connection with the countries lying to the west of the River Kali and engages never to have any concern with those countries or their inhabitants," according to Article 6 of the treaty. This demonstrates how the British employed territorial restrictions to reduce their security concerns, whether those fears were related to Nepal's ties with Sikhs or whether they were about Nepal's potential for alliance with Bengal or north India. Although the company's primary goal was trade, the idea of "political safety," which meant a dissuasion approach and wider areas of occupancy, sprang from it. The idea that Hastings invaded Nepal solely for business purposes is not supported by the data. It was a calculated move. In the midst of the disintegrating Mughal Empire, he was suspicious of the Hindu renaissance and the unity of the Gurkhas, Sikhs, and Marathas. He was planning pre-emptive conquest plans against the Marathas in central India, and in order to avoid fighting on two fronts, he wanted to first weaken Nepal. P.J. Marshal explains why it was a bad strategy: "Military readiness was a prerequisite for political safety. Military spending from 1761–1762 to 1770–1771 accounted for 44% of the 22 million pounds spent overall. The majority of

- soldiers who aspired to become politicians and governor-generals hardly grasped the difference between war and diplomacy and trade and improvement. Their first objective was Bengal's political safety, which they understood to mean enslaving Mysore, the Marathas, the Pindaris, the Nepalese, and the Burmese.
- f. **War preparation: Pre-war opinions:**"They will not rest satisfied without establishing their own power and authority, and will unite with the hill rajas, whom we have dispossessed," said Amar Singh Thapa, who was not alone in opposing the Kathmandu Durbar's request for Nepalese chiefs' opinions regarding a potential war with the British. We have only hunted deer up to this point; if we fight this battle, we will have to ready to fight tigers. He opposed the policies of Butwal and Sheeraj, claiming that they were the product of self-centred individuals who were reluctant to take the country to war in order to satisfy their own desires. Nepal is Prime Minister Bhimsen Thapa, on the other hand, asserts, "Our hills and our forts are form by the hands of God and are impregnable." As recommended by Amar Singh, Bhimsen Thapa It is hardly unexpected that Thapa has this attitude. The families of Butwal and Sheeraj were the ones that profited the most from his usurpations. Prinsep calculates that, depending on how they repossessed the land, the Nepalese may have made at least 100,000 rupees annually from it. Therefore, the aspirational beliefs of Nepal's influential figure Bhimsen did not include the preservation of this income. Thapa continues to have an impact on his family. The prime minister of Nepal admitted that the Nepalese had a number of advantages over the British, including local knowledge and previous experience fighting in difficult terrain. However, the British possessed considerably more advanced weapons and a numerical advantage. Additionally, the Governor-General foolishly thought, "the difficulties of mountain warfare were greater on the defensive side than on that of a well conducted offensive operation." According to soldiers like Rollo Gillespie, "Opinion is everything in such a country as India: and whenever the natives shall begin to lose their reverence for the English arms, our superiority in other respects will quickly sink into contempt." This was in reference to the Nepalese as a threat to British supremacy.
- g. **Finance:**The governor requested 20 million rupees from the Nawab of Awadh in order to finance the upcoming war with Nepal. He wrote about Sadat Ali's unexpected death. He voluntarily offered me one billion rupees, which I transferred to his sovereignty over Oude, but he declined as a peishcush, or tribute, to the members of the Honourable

Company. It turned out, however, that his successor fully understood what I had tentatively discussed with him. His 8 lacs was then added to this sum, bringing the total interest to 6%, which is equal to donations given to other Nawaz family branches. The UK government promised to pay for this without requiring any withdrawals. The money thus acquired was placed in the Treasury, from which it was intended to take out the amounts required to meet the urgent needs of the service. Calcutta informed me shortly after that it had been deemed convenient for him to use 5.4 million yen of the money he had received from me to pay back his 8% loan, which did not surprise me. The remaining ones were necessary for the current goal, and it was hoped that the Nawab would provide more assistance to the war's targets. The Council did not anticipate that I would have any immediate difficulties by disposing of the first sum because this occurred early in the fall and actions against Nepal could not begin until mid-November. Fortunately, I was on such good terms with the Nawab Vizier that I could fairly explain my situation to him. In order to provide the Honourable Company with more than two million and a half sterling on my easy receipt, he promised to provide an additional crore.

- h. **In the aftermath of the war, he writes:** The Nawab Vizier's dominions surrounded the wealthiest area of the land we had taken. I arranged for him to receive that tract in exchange for the second crore that I had borrowed. Out of the crore, fifty-two lacs were used for war expenses. Of that amount, forty-eight lacs (£600,000) remained in the treasury, which clearly benefited the Honourable Company and prevented future irritation from an impudent neighbour. The Nepalese, on the other hand, had gradually depleted their treasury due to the massive sums of money they had spent on the first and second wars against the Tibetans.

- i. **Terrain:** An unnamed British soldier sums up the formidability of the topology. The region that is under Nepal's jurisdiction is a hilly region that lies between Tibet and the Ganges Valley. It is only a hundred miles wide, yet it is almost the entire length of the British dominions' northwest border. They possessed a section of the plain below the hills that was irregularly wide and known as the Nepal Turrye, but it was unclear when the acquisition was completed. Extremely challenging is the country's overall military character. The Great Saul Forest, which stretches for an average width of ten or twelve miles, covers the plain immediately in front of the hills. The mountains are enormous, with steep sides

and dense, impenetrable jungle. Usually watercourses, the trenches on these ridges are more like gulfs or chasms than anything deserving of the word valley is. The roads are extremely unsafe and always cross-mountains or riverbeds; hill porters are the primary mode of transportation throughout the entire country. Despite this broad description, there should be areas that are somewhat open and hollow, as well as elevated areas of reasonably level terrain, but they should be so far away that they do not really help with sexual relations. The Nepal Proper Valley is one of the biggest and most productive of these. There is a challenging area to Nepal's west until the country opens up once more in the Gorkha Valley, which was once own by the current monarchy. – The country is challenging westward until the Kemaon district sees some improvement. The Dhoon Valley, Sue-na-Ghur's area, and the more recent conquests that extended to the settlement where Umar Sing, a chief with extraordinary abilities, commanded and in fact wielded an authority nearly independent, are all located further west.

- ii. **British plan of operation:** The first British operation involved two fronts of attack over a 1,500-kilometer (930-mile) border between the Sutlej and the Koshi. Major-Generals John Sullivan Wood and Bennet Marley led their columns across the Terai to the centre of the Kathmandu valley on the eastern front. On the western front, Colonel David Ochterlony and Major-General Rollo Gillespie commanded columns. The Nepalese army, led by Amar Singh Thapa, confronted these columns. The British forces started to deploy toward various depots at the beginning of October 1814. The army was quickly divided into four divisions: one at Benares, one at Meerut, one at Dinapur, and one at Ludhiana. Major-General Marley led the first division, which was the largest at Dinapur. Its goal was to capture the pass at Makwanpur, which is the key to Nepal and lies between Gunduk and Baghmati. The goal was to advance to Kathmandu, so bringing the conflict directly into the enemy's homeland. His Majesty's 24th foot of 907 men were among the 8,000 troops in this army. Four 18-pounders, eight 6- and 3-pounders, and fourteen mortars and howitzers were part of the train. Major General Wood is second Benares Division then retreated to Gorakhpur, marched via the Bhootnuill Pass into the hills, turned east, and joined the first Division in the highlands as they marched towards Kathmandu. The enemy's army was

supposed to split the second division in half and prevent communication between the capital and the entire Kumaon and Garhwal army. They had 4,494 troops in total, including 950 men from His Majesty's 17th Infantry and roughly 3,000 infantry. In addition to his own seven 3-pounder guns and a 6-pounder, it also had four mortars and howitzers for backup. Major General Gillespie commanded the third division, which was formed at Meerut and was to march straight to Dehradun. After demolishing the forts in this valley, he either headed west or took the position of Nahan, the capital of Sirmour, where Ranjore Singh Thapa succeeded his father Amar Singh, or he marched east to recover Srinagar from Amar Singh Thapa's army since it looked more practical. After separating this chief from the others, he went to face him at the Sutlej River. Originally made up of His Majesty's 53rd Division, this division had 3,513 men total—roughly 1,000 Europeans and 2,500 native infantry—as well as artillery and a few dismounted dragoons. The north western division, Ludhiana's fourth division, was supposed to function in the hilly regions close to Sutlej. They were gathered under Brigadier General Ochterlony's leadership and stationed in and around the capital Archi. Their mission was to advance against the formidable and vast positions held by Amar Singh and Major General Gillespie, his direct subordinate. I was told to descend because Amar Singh would encircle and expel this force if these positions were taken. This 5,993-man army was made up completely of indigenous infantry and artillery. It had four mortars and howitzers, ten 6-pounders, and a platoon of two 18-pounders. Finally, Major Latter was equipped with two thousand soldiers, including his district battalion, to defend the Poornea frontier eastward beyond the Koshi River. Without actually advancing troops for the purpose, this officer wanted to establish contact with the Raja of Sikkim and provide him with all the support and encouragement he needed to drive the Gorkhas out of the eastern slopes. After a successful attempt to keep the Gorkhas within their own borders, Captain Barré Latter was dispatched to the frontier with Poornea. He completed the Anglo-Sikkimese Treaty of Titaliaa, which confirmed the Raja's dominions, although he lost territory from his border to the Tamur River. The Commander-in-Chief of the British forces was Lord Moira. All four divisions composed mostly of Indian Sepoy. Ochterlony's army was the only division without a single British

battalion. In conclusion, the Gorkhali Army defeated the BriLord Moira was the British forces' Commander-in-Chief. The majority of the Sepoy in all four categories are Indian. The only division without a single British battalion was the Ochterlony army. Ultimately, the Gorkhali Army lost the other two fronts in the west while defeating the British on three fronts, including the middle and east British on three fronts consisting the middle and the east whereas lost the remaining two fronts in the west.

35. **Battle of Makwanpur Gadhi:** Before moving on to Kathmandu, Major General Marley was sent to take control of Hetauda and seize the fortifications of Makwanpur and Hariharpur. Between the Rapati and Baghmati rivers was his frontage of advance. He had 12,000 soldiers for his onslaught against the Makwanpur and Hariharpur axis after more reinforcements. Despite the establishment of a large offensive base, Major General Marley was reluctant to take chances with the Nepalese. There were already some skirmishes going on. Likewise, the British Indian Army's Tiger, Major General George Wood, demonstrated extreme caution when facing the fiercely attacking Nepalese. The Makwanpur-Hariharpur axis was to be commanded by Colonel Ranabir Singh Thapa, the younger brother of Bhimsen Thapa. About 4,000 warriors, armed with antique rifles and some cannon components, occupied his spacious citadel. British troops, however, were unable to cross the border. Colonel Ranabir Singh Thapa attempted to entice the enemy to the location he had selected for execution. Major General Wood, however, eventually made his way back to Betiya after refusing to abandon Bara Gadhi.
36. **Battle of Jitgadh:** Major General Wood intended to march on Siu Raj, Jit Gadhi, and Nuwakot with the assistance of an overthrown Palpali king in order to go around the Butwal defences, drive out small opposition along the axis, and attack Palpa from a flank that was less fortified. Colonel Ujir Singh Thapa of Nepal had his 1200 soldiers spread out across a number of defensive locations, such as Jit Gadhi, Nuwakot Gadhi, and Kathe Gadhi. Colonel Ujir was a capable and committed leader and his troops were well-behave. He was well verse in mountain tactics and well known for taking use of advantages in people, material resources, and natural resources. On January 6, 1814, the British advanced to Jit Gadhi. As they crossed the Tinau River on their way to this castle, from the fortress, the Nepalese soldiers started shooting. Another column of assault was taking Tansen Bazar. The General was force to retreat to

Gorakhpur due to Nepalese spoiling attacks. In Nuwakot pakhe Gadhi, almost 70 Nepalese people perished. In the meantime, about 300 enemy soldiers were kill.

37. **Battle of Hariharpur Gadhi:** During the first campaign, Hariharpur Gadhi stronghold had not seen any unique military activity. Both Major General George Wood and Major General Bennet Marley had failed to go forward for an attack on the fortifications of Makwanpur and Hariharpur Gadhi.
38. **Battle of Nalapani:** The Anglo-Nepalese War began with the Battle of Nalapani. Nalapani Fort, which was under siege by British forces from October 31, 1814, to November 30, 1814, was the site of this conflict. Major General Rollo Gillespie, a veteran of the Battle of Java, led the attacking British forces while Captain Balbhadra Singh Thapa oversaw the garrison at the fort. As he rallied his troops to defeat Balbhadra Singh Thapa and his 600-man garrison on the first day of the siege, Gillespie was kill. According to reports, this garrison contained courageous women who used weapons to protect themselves from shells and bullets, despite the fact that they were vastly superior in both areas. For more than a month, Balbhadra Singh Thapa and his 600-man garrison managed to repel a British army of almost 5,000 soldiers, overpowering them in both numbers and weaponry. Fraser described the current state of affairs as follows:

Particularly in light of the atrocities of the latter half of the time, the resolute resolve of a tiny party to retain this modest office for more than a month in the face of such a relatively strong force should inspire appreciation from all quarters. The heart-breaking sight of their slain friends, the agony of their spouses and children who had walled themselves in, and the desperate sense of relief removed any motivation for their obstinate defence other than that which resulted from a strong feeling of duty backed by unfathomable heroism. The Kalunga garrison's attitude during the siege was definitely influence by this kind gesture for the enemy. There was no cruelty to the injured or POWs here, regardless of the character of the Gorkhas in other districts. Arrows that were poisoned were not use. There was no contamination in the water or wells. They did not appear to be animate by a ferocious spirit of vengeance. In the silence of real warfare, they displayed a liberal civility befitting a more civilized people and fought us honestly like human beings. Rather of showing disdain for the deceased and injured, they simply left their remains there until they were remove, and as is frequently the case, none of them had stripes. The British tried to force the garrison to surrender by cutting off the

fort's external water supply after two expensive and fruitless efforts to take the fort by frontal attack. After three days of being thirsty, Balbhadra led the 70 remaining garrison men in an assault on the besieging troops on the final day of the siege because he would not surrender. The survivors fled into the surrounding hills after fighting their way out of the fort. The conflict established the framework for the remainder of the Anglo-Nepalese War, and several subsequent battles, such as the one at Jaithak, followed suit. The British were so uneasy by the incident at Nalapani that Lord Hastings changed his original plan of action to avoid sending a portion of this division to occupy Garhwal. As a result, he gave Colonel Mawbey orders to move his entire army against Amar Singh's son, Colonel Ranjore Singh Thapa, who was at Nahan with roughly 2300 Gurkha army elite, and to leave a few troops in a solid position for the occupation of the Doon. Major-General Martindell was given command, and there were plans to significantly strengthen the division. Colonel Carpenter was station at Kalsee, at the north western tip of the Doon, while Colonel Mawbey led the division back via the Keree pass. This location was ideal for gathering intelligence because it controlled the Jumna passes on the primary route between the eastern and western Gurkha territories.

39. **Battle of Jaithak:** At this point, Major General Martindale joined the force and assumed command. On December 27, he began his assault on the Jaithak fort and took control of the village of Nahan. Ranjore Singh Thapa, the son of Amar Singh Thapa, commanded a garrison of two thousand troops in the fort. The Nepalese successfully repelled the British attack, and the initial assault ended in catastrophe. The second succeeded in cutting off the fort's water supply, but was unable to take it due mostly to the troops' fatigue and ammunition shortage. After reconsidering, Martindale ordered a withdrawal. Much later in the conflict, once Ochterlony had assumed leadership, Jaithak was finally capture. The British lost over three hundred soldiers in a single day of fighting at Jaithak, and Martin Dell's fierce enthusiasm for combat was dampen He declined to take any more action against the Nepalese army for more than a month and a half. As a result, by mid-February, Gillespie had died, Marley had defected, Wood had been hound into inaction, and Martindell had become nearly unable due to excessive caution, out of the four British commanders the Nepalese army had seen up to that point. It prepared the ground for Ochterlony to quickly prove himself and turn the tide of the conflict.

40. **Trying times for Nepalese troops:** The Nepalese were hopelessly overburdened out west. A tiny force of roughly 750 men, with an equal number of Kumaonis irregulars, held Kumaon, a vital conduit for Nepalese army contacts with the Far West. This was enough to protect an entire province. Furthermore, Doti, located east of Kumaon, had all but been deprived of troops. As Kumaon's governor, Bam Shah was ultimately in charge of the province's defence. The Nepalese army defenders were swiftly outmanoeuvred and forced to leave one station after another by the British force, which at first numbered around 4,500 soldiers. The Nepalese army was unable to stop the British advance even after they decisively defeated Captain Hearsay's brigade, which had been sent on a flanking drive through Eastern Kumaon, and captured the captain. Hasti Dal Shah brought a small contingent of reinforcement troops to Almore. Four additional companies were sent from Kathmandu to support the embattled Kumaon defences, but they were unable to reach the area in time to provide any assistance due to communication issues across the hills. Against less than 1,000 Nepalese army soldiers, Hastings sent Colonel Nicolls, the British troops' quartermaster-general in India, to lead the Almore campaign. He also sent two thousand regular troops to the front in addition to the large number of irregulars already stationed there. About five hundred members of the Nepalese Army, including Hasti Dal Shah, had left Almore to guard Alomar's northern communications route to Kathmandu. They intercepted this party. The most skilled Nepalese commander in this area, Hasti Dal Shah, was killed in the first seconds of the conflict. The losses experienced by the Nepalese were tremendous. The defenders at Almore were taken aback when they learned of this catastrophe. The Nepalese were powerless to stop the British advance as they drew up on Almore. On April 25, 1815, a band of irregular troops led by Col. Gardiner and 2,000 British regulars under Col. Nicholls attacked and took control of the town of Almore's heights. The British then succeeded in setting up gun positions at Almore within seventy yards of the fort's gate, and their cannon destroyed the fort's walls at close range. On April 27, 1815, Bam Shah turned himself in at Almore. The province of Kumaon and all of its strongholds were forced to surrender because of this British triumph.
41. **Second Battle of Malaon and Jaithak:** The Nepalese lines of communication between Central Nepal and the Far West were severed during the second battle of Malaon and Jaithak. Additionally, it guaranteed Ranajor Singh Thapa's and Kazi Amar Singh Thapa's dooms at Jaithak and Malaon. Major-General Ochterlony advanced extremely cautiously at Malaon, calling in heavy artillery and reinforcements from Delhi until his entire attack force was composed of almost 10,000 men, all of whom were well-equipped with heavy cannon. Singh, Kazi

Amar Because Bilaspur in the lowlands was essential to Thapa's food supply from his position in the Malaon Hills; the hills' topography compelled him to disperse his soldiers widely in an effort to protect every viewpoint. After cutting off Ballarpur's food supply, Ochterlony focused on the complex system of defensive positions that were built to withstand any frontal attack. Rear defences protected these stations, but none of them could sustain a prolonged heavy artillery barrage. Ochterlony had enough soldiers to attack and overrun multiple sites at once, which may potentially split the sparsely populated Nepalese defences. Ochterlony chose his target, a point on the ridge, and then proceeded to move slowly, consolidating each position that he took, and allowing the pioneers time to build roads so that the heavy guns could be moved forward to support each attack. After a series of carefully not over a thousand yards from Kazi Amar Singh Thapa's main fort at Malaon, he was able to secure a position on the crest of Deothal by well-planned and performed manoeuvres. Bhakti Thapa, an elderly warrior, bravely led attack after attack on this fortification, but he was kill in combat and the position remained intact. The British, greatly pleased by Bhakti's unwavering bravery in the face of insurmountable circumstances, returned his remains with full military honor as a token of their gratitude and respect. The British would finally be able to position themselves and their heavy weapons on a vantage point within range of Ranajor Singh's defences due to their numerical superiority. As a result, when Bam Shah's letter announcing the loss of Almore arrived, Kazi Amar Singh Thapa and Ranajor Singh Thapa were both surrounded and staring down the barrels of the British guns. Even though the old leader was still hesitant to give up, Kazi Amar Singh Thapa finally realized how hopeless things were and, forced by the situation and the British guns, gave up with honor for both Ranajor Singh and himself. On May 15, 1815, the British took over the Nepalese outposts in the Far West.

42. **Second Campaign:** The Western Front, or the districts of Garhwal and Kumaon, was where the enlarged Nepal Army was station. At last, Ochterlony outwitted Bada Kazi Amar Singh Thapa. In the first campaign of the Nepali Company, he was the only British commander to be successful. It should come as no surprise that Lord Moira once more named Amar Singh Thapa as the primary operational commander for the second assault on the Bharatpur-Makwanpur-Hariharpur front, which involved an invasion force of 17,000 men, the most of whom were Indian sepoy. On November 28, Nepal was given a 15-day ultimatum by the British to approve a treaty. However, the Nepalese found it extremely difficult to swiftly ratify the treaty's provisions. The British used the delay as justification to launch their second military offensive against the

monarchy. Bhimsen Thapa's brother, Colonel Bhakta war Singh Thapa, has been named Sector Commander for the first campaign's defensive battles in the region spanning from Bijayapur to Sindhuli Gadhi. Bada Kaji Amarsingh Thapa served as the Sector Commander over the eastern front and Sindhuli Gadhi during this second campaign. Makwanpur Gadhi was home to Colonel Bhaktawar Singh Thapa's headquarters. Major General David Ochterlony led a force of 17,000 British soldiers against Nepal, attacking the Upardang Gadhi, Sinchyang Gadhi, Kandrang Gadhi, Makwanpur Gadhi, and Hariharpur Gadhi fronts. Ochterlony made the decision to use a pass across the mountains that is rarely use during the February 1816 campaign. For the British, the failure there would have been disastrous. However, the British would be able to assault the Nepalese from behind if the passage was successful. To get to Hariharpur Gadhi, Colonels Kelly and O'Halloran followed the Baghmati River. A few village chiefs were bought off for confidential information regarding the defensive positions at Hariharpur Gadhi. The Nepalese defences were significantly jeopardize by the information. Even if the adversary could have only obtained a battalion, they would still have had an advantage thanks to secret routes. But it took more than a brigade's strength for the British to advance. On February 29, Colonel Kelly and Colonel O'Halloran attacked from two separate angles. The Nepalese army was ultimately driven out of Hariharpur Gadi following a fierce struggle. After retiring under Sindhuli Gadi, Kazi Ranjore Singh Thapa teamed up with Bada Kazi Amar Singh Thapa. By the end of March 1816, the British had withdrawn to Makwanpur and had not ventured to Sindhuli Gadi. A treaty was eventually sign because the situation between Nepal and Britain got so dire. At Kathmandu Durbar, Chandra Sekhar Upadhyaya, Pandit Gajaraj Mishra, and Bhaktawar Singh Thapa signed the treaty, which Major General David Ochterlony sat down to receive. Two days later, the ratified treaty was given to the British in Makwanpur. The Treaty of Sugauli, which has been view as an unfair agreement, ended the war and cost Nepal a third of its land. Nepal's new eastern and western borders are the Mechi and Mahakali rivers, respectively.

43. **The Treaty of Sugauli:** On March 4, 1816, the Treaty of Sugauli was ratify. According to the terms of the treaty, Nepal lost the Western Terai, Kumaon, and Garhwal regions, as well as all of Sikkim, including Darjeeling. The kingdom's new eastern and western borders were establish by the Mechi and Mahakali rivers, respectively. A yearly payment of 200,000 rupees would be made by the British East India Company to make up for the loss of revenue from the Terai region. Resident was establish by the British. In the end, the concern of having a British resident in Kathmandu was unjustified because the Nepali rulers were able to isolate the resident to the

point that they effectively placed him under house arrest. The Terai territory, however, proved challenging for the British to control; as a result, some of it was ultimately returned to the kingdom in 1816, and yearly payments were eliminated. However, the border dispute between the two nations persisted even after the Anglo-Nepalese war was over. It was not until 1830 that the boundary between Oudh and Nepal was finally changed. For many years later, the two governments continued to address the problem between Nepal and the British territories. The British never intended to undermine the independence or existence of a state that served as a valuable buffer between themselves and China's dependents. For fear of upsetting China, whose vassal Nepal was in principle, Lord Hastings had abandoned his intention to split Nepal. A high-ranking Manchu official led a sizable military force from China to Lhasa in 1815, during a British campaign in far western Nepal. The next year, following the signing of the Anglo-Nepalese treaty, the Chinese army went south once more, all the way to the Nepali border. Because the Chinese invasion of 1792 was still fresh in their minds and there was a rush of urgent diplomatic action, the Nepalese panicked. Hastings instructed the British resident who had just arrived in Kathmandu to pack his belongings and be prepared to go immediately in the event of another Chinese invasion. He also sent reassuring messages to the imperial authorities.

44. **Cost of war:**The Gurkha War actually cost more than the sum of the campaigns against the Marathas and the Pindaris, for which Lord Moira's government is best known: Rs. 5,156,961 compared to Rs. 3,753,789. This was true even though Lord Moira boasted to the British parliament that he had expanded the state coffers. This type of information had a significant impact on the company government's policies in the years that followed. As a result, although if the Company Government in principle fully supported the growth of trade between Western Tibet and its territories, particularly in shawl wool, it was not ready to take any concrete action to make this happen. It intended to prevent the possibility of another costly hill war, however remote, and preferred to leave the Chinese in Tibet to their own ways. Additionally, despite having direct access to wool-growing regions, post-war British merchants were unable to realize their dreams of a shawl wool trade. It was too late, British traders understood. The market for scarf wool was tightly controlled and highly regulated. Merchants from Ladakh and Kashmir controlled it, and the only outsider they had to deal with was Maharaja Ranjit Singh, the strong Sikh leader of Lahore. In this period of crisis and uncertainty, Ranjit was the last person Britain could offend since he was fiercely protective of his rights. Thus, no shawl wool was ever sent to the East India Company. It had long since stopped trading when it eventually gained Punjab and

Kashmir following the Sikh Wars in the 1840s, and Kashmir was so lowly valued that it was promptly thrown away, sold to the Raja of Jammu for a pittance.

45. **Gorkhas in World War 1:** Known for being the birthplace of the Gurkhas, a fabled warrior tribe, the hill-town district of Gorkha is situated in the Himalayan republic of Nepal, sandwiched between the two Asian giants of China and India. The hill tribes of Sunwar, Gurung, Rai, Magar, and Limbu, among others, are the main source of the combatants. Their battle cry, "Ayo Gorkhali" (which means, "The Gorkhas are here") and motto, "It's better to die than to be a coward," made the warriors who wielded kukris (long-curved knives) infamous. According to legend, a Gurkha must draw blood after drawing the kukhri. "They are famous because of their bravery, loyalty, and simplicity," says Tikendra Dewan, chairperson of the British Gurkha Welfare Society (BGWS), based in the UK. According to former Indian army Chief Sam Manekshaw, "If a man says he is not afraid of dying, he is either lying or is a Gorkha." They are also well known for their fearlessness. As part of an agreement made by the three nations at the time of Indian independence in 1947, the combatants are currently serving in the militaries of Nepal, India, and the United Kingdom. Approximately 3500 Gorkhas are now serving in the British army, compared to about 120,000 Gorkhas who are recruited in the Indian military. The Gorkha community stepped up and pressed its men to the Commonwealth's disposal at the start of World War 1. In order to replace British Indian Army soldiers who had left to fight abroad, more than 16,000 Gorkhas were later deployed to India as garrison battalions and on the North-West Front. Approximately 100,000 Gurkhas joined the Gurkha Brigade's regiments. They battled and lost their lives. Mesopotamia, Persia, Egypt, Gallipoli, Palestine, France and Flanders, and Salonika. At the Loos, a battalion of the eighth Gurkhas distinguished itself by fighting to the end and, as the Indian Corps Commander put it, "found its Valhalla." At Gallipoli, the sixth Gurkhas achieved immortal glory when the Turks captured the area that would subsequently be known as "Gurkha Bluff." The only forces in the entire campaign to reach and maintain the crest line and gaze down on the Straits, the campaign's ultimate goal, were at Sari Bair. As stated in the preface to the second volume of the sixth Gurkha's history by Field Marshal Sir William Slim. In Gallipoli in 1915, I had my first encounter with the sixth Gurkha Rifles. I decided to serve with them if the chance arose because I was so impressed by their demeanour throughout one of the most desperate conflicts in history. When it finally arrived four years later, I spent several of the most joyful and, from a military perspective, most valuable years of my life in the Regiment.

Rifleman Kulbir Thapa, the most well-known Gurkha, was awarded a Victoria Cross for his valour at the Battle of Loos in 1915.

- a. Only the strongest: With over 28,000 young men vying for 200 spots each year, the British hiring procedure is regarded as one of the most difficult in the world. The young people must run about five kilometres over difficult terrain while carrying nearly twenty-five pounds of rocks on their backs in less than an hour in order to pass the exam. Gurkhas were sent back to Nepal, nevertheless, because they were denied permanent status in the UK despite having served in the British military. Compared to their fellow British soldiers, they receive a smaller pension. The London government's decision to provide equal pensions to all Gurkha soldiers who retired after 1997, however, changed the situation in 2007. The warriors' fight for equality saw a small win with the move. All retired Gurkhas were granted the right to reside in the UK a few years later, in 2009.
- b. Joining the British: The British East India Company's battle against Nepal in 1814–16 marked the Gurkhas' first encounter with the West. Despite the British triumph at the end of the war, the Gurkhas severely damaged their army. "In my life, I have never witnessed such bravery or steadiness. Even though their friends were dying heavily all around them, they refused to run and appeared unfazed by death, according to a British soldier's recollections. The foundation for the nearly two centuries of military ties between the two sides was thus laid when the British, impressed by the fighting prowess of their adversaries, included a clause in the peace treaty they signed with the then-Nepali King that permitted them to enlist Gurkhas to serve in the British army.
- c. First time in Europe: Few people could have predicted at the time that the Gurkhas would be fighting with the British Army during World War I (1914–1918), thousands of miles away from home. Nevertheless, it did occur, and over 200,000 Gurkhas served in the Great War, with their battalions serving on battlefields from France's trenches to Persia in modern-day Iran. Among the many past wars in which Nepalese soldiers have served for the United Kingdom, include World War II, the Falklands War, Iraq, and Afghanistan. However, the first time the Gurkhas left South Asia was during World War I, and official records show that Gurkha battalions lost more than 20,000 soldiers. The number of Gurkha rifle battalions increased to thirty-three during the war. "The government of Nepal realized how necessary the Gurkha soldiers were to the Allied campaign and they

made additional Gorkha units available for the British high command for service on all fronts," according to Benita Estevez, the author of the book "Gorkhas: Better to die than live a coward."

- d. Gallipoli campaign: According to Dewan, the Gurkhas and the rest of the British Indian Army faced a number of new difficulties as a result of the war in Europe, including trench warfare, frigid temperatures, and unfamiliar terrain. According to British general Sir James Willcocks: "Gurkhas were exposed to every form of terror, and they could reply only with their valour and the rifles and the two machine-guns per battalion with which they were armed (no trench mortars or hand grenades), and yet they did it. "The greatest contribution of the Gurkhas occurred in 1915 during the Gallipoli campaign, when the combatants achieved enduring fame by taking a heavily fortified Turkish position with comparatively few casualties—an event known as "Gurkha Bluff." A Gurkha battalion fought to the death and to the very last on the Western front during the Battle of Loos. Approximately 2,000 gallantry decorations were given to the battalions in recognition of their valour and wartime contributions. This statement from British Captain Ralph Turner, who fought with the Gurkhas, may best capture their valour and devotion to British military efforts during the Great military: "Bravest of the brave, most generous of the generous, never had country more faithful friends than you."

46. List of military operations involving Gurkhas:

- i. **First Anglo-Sikh War (India, 1846)**: The British and Punjab were at odds following the Anglo-Gorkha war. They both wished to stay out of trouble. However, the Sikh army engaged in combat with the British following the passing of Punjab's king, Ranjit Singh. The Sikhs invaded British territory at Sutlej in 1845. An inconclusive fight was fought at Ferozeshah in December 1846, and the Sikhs attempted to cut off British connection in January 1846. In response, a joint Gurkha, Indian, and British army was dispatched to stop the Sikhs. The Sikhs were compelled to leave. A final fight was fought at Sobraon the next month. The conflict involved Gurkha reinforcements from the Nasiri and Sir moor Battalions. After the Sikh army gave up, a peace deal was reached.
- ii. **Siege of Delhi (India, 1857)**: The siege of Delhi occurred between June and September of 1857. To put down the uprising, the British East India Company sent men to Delhi who had complaints against the British officers; this was the forerunner of the current Brigade of Gurkhas. The

battalion was given Queen's Truncheon during the conquest of Delhi. The Nepalese Army, which Jang Bahadur Rana sent to support the British, also engaged in combat during the invasion.

- iii. **Second Anglo-Afghan War (Afghanistan, 1878-1880):**The second Gurkha Rifles battalion engaged the Afghans in combat in the northern settlement. The British heavily influenced Afghanistan after the war.
- iv. **Third Anglo-Afghan War (Afghanistan, 1919):**On May 6, 1919, the British Indian government declared war on Afghanistan. For reinforcement, Gurkhas and Sikhs were dispatched to Landi Kotal.
- v. **Boxer rebellion (China, 1900):**In the Boxer Rebellion, the Gurkhas battled Chinese soldiers to put an end to the rebellion against foreign influence in China.
- vi. **Anglo-Iraqi War (Iraq, 1941):**Along with the second battalion 8th Gorkha Rifles, the second battalion 7th Gorkha Rifles, and the third battalion 11th Sikh Regiment, the 20th Indian Infantry Brigade landed at Basra on April 18, 1941. They engaged in combat in several Iraqi cities.
- vii. **Battle of Jitra (Malaysia, 1941):**The Gorkha army fought against the Japanese in Malaysia in 1941. All armies were moved to Singapore after the war was lost.
- viii. **Battle of Wadi Akarit (Tunisia, 1943):**On April 5 and 6, 1943, the Battle of Wadi Akarit was fought in Wadi Akarit, Tunisia. Supporting the Allied forces was the battle's main objective. Under the leadership of the Indian Fourth Division, Gorkha soldiers participated in the conflict. During a night-time assault on the Fatnassa Plateau, Lal Bahadur Thapa emerged victorious.
- ix. **Battle of Imphal (India, 1944):**The region around Imphal, the capital of the northern Indian state of Manipur, was the scene of the Battle of Imphal. Between March 12 and June 21, 1944, Japanese and British forces engaged in combat. Over 184 people were killed and 820 wounded in the action, which involved three battalions of the 10th Princess Mary's Own Gorkha Rifles. Following the war, the Royal Gurkha Rifles, the regiment that preceded it, were awarded the honor of Imphal.
- x. **Brunei revolt (Brunei, 1962-1966):**In December 1962, the first military force to be utilized against the Brunei Revolt was the first battalion of the second KEO Gurkha Rifles. In December, the troops were airdropped to Brunei. In Sarawak and Sabah, the Gurkhas engaged the Indonesian Regular Army in combat. The entire operation took four years. In 1966, the campaign ended. Rambahadur Limbu received a Victoria Cross in combat in November 1965 for trying to save two injured teammates.

- xi. **Battle of Sylhet (East Pakistan, 1971):**The Indian army's 4/5 Gorkha Rifles fought the Pakistani brigades in the Battle of Sylhet in East Pakistan (now Bangladesh) in 1971. On December 16, 1971, the Pakistani brigades surrendered because of the operation.
- xii. **Sri Lanka peacekeeping operation (Sri Lanka, 1987-1990):**The Indian Army's 4/5 Gorkha Rifles were sent to Sri Lanka as peacekeepers on October 1, 1987. They had to battle the rebels there, nevertheless. The Gurkha army initially saved the 13 Sikh Light Infantry and a group of 10 Para-commando. Following the rescue effort, the Gurkha army was attacked by the LTTE, and the protracted conflict began. The operation lasted until 1990.. The Indian army provided local Tamils with weapons to combat the LTTE during that time, and some Gurkha soldiers were assigned to train them. The Indian army had to withdraw from the operation that brought the Gurkha army back from Sri Lanka due to significant damage; Prem Thapa received the Param Vir Chakra for guiding the troops after his superiors were killed in one of the battles.
- xiii. **Falklands War (Argentina, 1982):**Argentina was the scene of the Falklands War in 1982. Argentina launched an invasion of the British-controlled Falkland Islands on April 2, 1982. A navy task force sailed to the island in retaliation. Gurkhas were assigned to capture Mount William during the conflict. The Gurkhas suffered multiple injuries because of the Argentine artillery assault. At the end of the war, every Argentine force on the Falklands gave up.
- xiv. **North Africa (Arabia, 1943):**Gurkha forces in Arabia, North Africa, attacked Turkish soldiers. When the vital port of Tubrik fell, Gurkhas were sent to guard it; they were captured by the Germans and suffered losses. To fend off the Germans, the surviving men were sent to the mountainous region. Rommel's Africa Corps surrendered following the battle.
- xv. **Italy campaign (Italy, 1944):**In order to stop the Germans from moving forward, the Gurkha infantry were dispatched to Italy in May 1943. When the Allied forces landed, Italy gave up, but the German soldiers stayed in the Italian Alps. As members of the fourth Indian Division, the Gurkhas arrived in Italy on February 11, 1944. The offensive began on February 16 and 17; both attacks resulted in 20% casualties and were unsuccessful. The Polish Division eventually occupied the position on May 14. The Gurkhas lost 4,000 men during that time, yet they were able to capture a number of mountains.
- xvi. **Kosovo operation (Kosovo, 1999):**In a NATO-led attack, the British Gurkhas disarmed seventy members of the Kosovo Liberation Army. In the Kacanik area, Kosovo Liberation Army members, who then launched a counterattack, fired upon the Gurkha troops. The Kosovar fighters turned themselves in with their weapons following the operation.

xvii. **Gorkhas on the frontline between India and China:**The relationship between the two most populous nuclear-armed nations in the world was shattered on June 15 by a clash between Indian and Chinese troops in the Galwan Valley in Ladakh but it also brought attention to the fact that Nepali soldiers served in the Indian Army. The relationship between the two most populous nuclear-armed nations in the world was shattered on June 15 by a clash between Indian and Chinese troops in the Galwan Valley in Ladakh, but it also brought attention to the fact that Nepali soldiers served in the Indian Army. The fighting, which claimed the lives of 20 Indian soldiers and an undetermined number of Chinese soldiers, sparked concerns about the geopolitical balance in South Asia, a region already unstable because to the COVID-19 pandemic. Following the Galwan Valley battle, Indian Army Chief Gen. Manoj Mukund Naravane said that Nepal was "acting at the behest of someone else," referring to China, in reference to Nepal's own border dispute with India over Limpiyadhura. However, given that over 30,000 Nepali Gorkha soldiers serve in the Indian army, many of whom are station in frontline positions along their borders, Nepal has an even greater stake in India's conflicts with China and Pakistan.

- i. Following the Sugauli Treaty of 1816 between the East India Company and the Gorkha Empire, the Indian Gorkha regiments were establish as a legacy for enlisting Nepali citizens in the British Army. Even before the war was over, the British raised ten Gurkha regiments, including one in 1815. At least 50,000 of them were kill in battle while fighting with the Allies in both World Wars. The Indian Army retained six regiments and four remained with the British Army after India attained independence in 1947. There are now seven Gurkha regiments in the Indian army. At least three significant conflicts have erupted since 1962 because of the ill-defined "Line of Actual Control" separating China and India. This month's altercation was the most severe to date. Although the exact number of Gorkhas who lost their lives in the 1962 Sino-Indian War is unknown, it is claim that 2,000 Indian soldiers were kill. An estimated 700 Gorkha soldiers were among the 4,000 Indian Army prisoners of war. Soldiers who had returned home to Nepal on leave were hurriedly call back earlier this month to join troop transport at the border, despite the fact that no Nepalis were killed in the conflict in the Galwan Valley. Despite the lockdown, they had to travel there from Palpa, Syangja, and other districts. Dilip Karki, a Nepali soldier in the Indian Army from

Gulmi, was killed in a gunfight on the India-Pakistan border in Jammu & Kashmir. The most recent death among Nepal's forces on the front lines in India. Both India and Nepal have pledged to use dialogue to defuse the Lumpyadhura conflict after the "war of the maps," but Nepal's Foreign Minister Pradeep Gyawali claims that India has not replied to multiple diplomatic letters requesting the start of discussions. The purpose of Prime Minister K P Oli's Sunday statement, in which he accused India of attempting to overthrow him, was to divert attention from issues inside his own party, but it would not improve relations with Delhi. A statement made by Defence Minister Ishwar Pokhrel that the Indian Army Chief had offended Nepal's Gorkha soldiers, who "lay down their lives to protect India," will also not be tolerated. Ashok Swain, an Indian professor of peace and conflict studies at Uppsala University in Sweden, recently tweeted a succinct summary of the subtleties of this delicate geopolitical triangle involving India, Nepal, and China: During the 1962 War, Nepali Gorkha forces led by Naik Subedar Jung Bahadur Gurung rescued India's Galwan Valley from China! In the week that Modi and Nepal were involved in a savage land conflict, China seized control of the same Galwan Valley. Stopping the recruitment of Nepalis into the Indian and British forces was one of the demands made by the Maoists in Nepal when they were fighting the monarchy underground. The ruling Nepal Communist Party currently includes some of the same Maoists. Numerous groups within Nepal's left-wing movement have repeatedly demanded that the Gurkha recruitment process be halted. According to Nishchal Nath Pandey of the Centre for South Asian Studies, "they point to the fact that Nepali citizens are employed to fight someone else's war." "Gurkha participation in international conflicts can be particularly contentious, considering Nepal's non-aligned foreign policy." In Nepal's interior, where the recruitment takes place, the rationale for ending the Gurkha recruiting process may be reasonable, but it will not be well received. Service in the Indian and British Armies is highly competitive, and soldiers' pensions and remittances from outside contribute significantly to Nepal's economy. According to a 2017 estimate by India's Manohar Parrikar Institute for Defence Studies and Analyses, Indian Gorkha regiments send \$1 billion annually to Nepal, with an additional \$800 million coming from pensions and arrears.

People from one nation fighting and dying for another, particularly when they are on opposing sides of a conflict with a friendly neighbour, may be an anachronism. Nonetheless, it seems that Nepal's leaders have determined that the nation cannot afford to lose remittances from the Indian and British Armies, particularly at a time when the pandemic is hurting the economy. "Their remittances to Nepal have revolutionized the rural economy," Pandey continues. The districts of Lamjung, Kaski, and Dhahran City are excellent illustrations of the wealth and splendour enjoyed by the families of Nepali troops serving in other forces. In addition to harming the Gurkhas' image for bravery and valour, stopping recruiting might also harm their ties with Britain and India. According to Bhaskar Koirala of the Nepal Institute for Strategic Studies, "The NCP should openly state that Gurkha recruitment should not occur in the British military if they are adamant that Nepalis should not be permitted to join Gorkha regiments in India." Koirala is sceptical that the Gurkha Brigade of the British Army will cease recruiting. "Gurkhas should be treated as an international symbol of Nepal," he argues. They are not a political card that Kathmandu politicians can manipulate, trade, or negotiate with. The Nepali administration has not done enough to change the perception of many Indians that the country is now firmly in the Chinese camp. Indeed, Oli has reaffirmed it with his remarks on Sunday. One of Nepal's key foreign policy tenets, according to experts, is the peaceful resolution of conflicts and equitable and cordial relations with both of its enormous neighbours. Nepal may potentially play a part in settling disputes between China and India. Nepal may be able to strengthen its position as an intermediary state by resolving tense relations with India and advancing relations with China through the India-China boundary conflict, thus winning over both Asian hegemons.

47. **Field Marshal Sam Manekshaw: The Proud Gorkha Who Fought Five Wars for India:** The first Indian Army officer to be elevated to the position of Field Marshal was Sam Hormusji Framji Jamshedji Manekshaw. Field Marshal Manekshaw, sometimes referred to as Sam Bahadur (Sam the Brave), was a witty and direct individual. On the anniversary of his birth, here are some facts about the courageous officer.

- i. He was train in the first batch of the Indian Military Academy in 1932. He has earlier wanted to be a doctor, just like his father.
- ii. He took part in five wars for the country - World War II, 1947 Indo-Pak War, 1962 Indo-China War, 1965 Indo-Pak War and 1971 Indo-Pak War.
- iii. The unit he was serving in during the second world war, the 4 Battalion of 12 Frontier Force Regiment, went to Pakistan Army after partition. By the end of 1947 he was posted to 3/5 Gorkha Rifles.
- iv. The political leadership did not faze him. He allegedly told VK Menon to refrain from asking officers what they thought about their seniors. In 1971, when Indira Gandhi asked him “General are you ready?” (For war), he reply: “I am always ready sweetie”.
- v. He was the tactician behind India’s victory in 1971 war. When he was asked to go to East Pakistan to accept the surrender of the Pakistan Army, he declined and said the honour should go to his army commander in the East, Lt. Gen. Jagjit Singh Aurora.
- vi. Pakistan military ruler Yahya Khan, Manekshaw junior in 1947, never paid him the money for his motorcycle he took from him. Manekshaw recalled the event and said: "I never received the Rs 1000, but he gave me the whole of East Pakistan."
- vii. Injured in war in Burma, he was rescue by his orderly and taken to a surgeon. Seven bullets were remove from his body. When the surgeon asked him what had happened to him, he retorted that he was “kicked by a mule”.
- viii. A proud Gorkha officer, he had reportedly commented that “If a man says he is not afraid of dying, he is either lying or he is a Gorkha”.

48. India: Remembering Gorkha contributions to Independence Movement: The Indian Gorkha community has made enormous sacrifices and contributions to our nation-building and freedom struggle. As our country celebrates "Azadi ka Amrit Mahotsav," led by Prime Minister Narendra Modi, we pause to honor the courageous individuals who gave their lives to ensure that we might live in a free land. All communities in the country actively participated in the fight for independence, but little is known about the contributions of smaller communities, particularly those in north eastern India. All of that is changing, as more and more people from smaller areas and groups are learning about the freedom fighters thanks to Prime Minister Modi's "Azadi ka Amrit Mahotsav" remembrance. Unfortunately, most people in our country are ignorant of the sacrifices made by our Gorkha forebears. The Indian Gorkha community has made enormous

contributions to our nation-building and freedom struggle. Here is my modest attempt to highlight some of the icons from the Indian Gorkha community whose contributions to the history of India's independence are still largely unknown to the public, as I am a Gorkha by ethnicity and a Member of Parliament from the Darjeeling Lok Sabha constituency, which is the centre of the Gorkha community in India.

- a. **Capt. Ram Singh Thakuri – Himachal Pradesh**: Perhaps the most well-known and little known of the several well-known Gorkha freedom warriors was Captain Ram Singh Thakuri of Himachal Pradesh. Identify it as fate or coincidence: On August 15, 1914, Captain Thakuri was born into a Gorkha family in Khaniara village, Dharamshala, Pradesh, Himachal. He became a unit musician with the 2/1 Gorkha Rifles in 1924. He was a gifted young man who was very good at many things, like wrestling, track and field, and soccer. His battalion was sent to Singapore during World War II. The Japanese took over the Allied forces when Singapore fell in 1942. Captain Ram Singh Thakuri enlisted in the Indian National Army (INA) during this time. His musical ability quickly gained popularity, and Netaji himself noticed it. Knowing that music may have an impact on soldiers' morale, Netaji, a shrewd military strategist, requested that the INA organize a brass band. The most well-known songs from India's freedom campaigns, Captain Thakuri, who did not disappoint Netaji, produced including Kadam Kadam Badhaye Ja, Sare Jahan se Accha, Inquilab Zindabad, Hind Sipahi, the Rani of Jhansi Regiment marching song "Hum Bharat ki Ladki Hai," and others. The Azad Hind leadership was adamant that a national anthem was necessary, one that would unite all Indians by means of a shared. Some preferred the national song, "Vande Mataram," by the renowned poet Ban Kim Chandra Chatterjee, but others thought it was insufficiently inclusive. Captain Lakshmi Sahgal, who had it played at the INA women's wing conference that Netaji had attended, first exposed Netaji to Gurudev Rabindranath Tagore's "Jana Gana Mana". After that, Netaji gave Captain Ram Singh Thakuri instructions to rework Gurudev Rabindranath Tagore's Jana Gana Mana music into a marching song that INA men could follow. "The song should have such an indelible impact and force that the Cathay Building (in Singapore) should 'break' into two parts and the sky should become visible," Captain Thakuri recalled with fondness in one of his conversations with Netaji. "While Captain Abid Ali and Mumtaz Hussain rewrote Gurudev "Jana Gana Mana" to

“शुभसुखचैन – Capt. Ram Singh Thakuri provided the music for "Subha Skhuh Chain ki Barsha Barse." Under Netaji's leadership, the Provisional Free Government of India (Arzi Hukumat-e-Azad Hind) adopted Subha Skhuh Chain ki Barsha Barse as the national anthem, or Qaumi Tarana. When the INA came to power on October 31, 1943, the orchestra under Capt. Thakuri played the Qaumi Tarana, and the Cathay Building did indeed resonate thunderously, "Subha Sukh Chain" was play as the national anthem of free India for the first time on September 11, 1942, in Hamburg. Our present national anthem, Jana Gana Mana, is based on the music of Capt. Our present national anthem, Jana Gana Mana, is based on the music of Capt. Thakuri's "Qaumi Tarana." Capt. Thakuri received a gold medal from Subhas Chandra Bose in 1944 in recognition of his service. Additionally, Netaji sent Captain Thakuri a saxophone and a violin as personal presents. When Pt. Jawaharlal Nehru unfurled the Tiranga from Lal Quila on August 15, 1947, Captain Thakuri was specifically summon to play the "Qaumi Tarana." He did so using the violin that Netaji had given him, telling him, "You will play this violin when India gets her Independence." Regretfully, the governments of the time disregarded the valiant INA Freedom Fighters after independence. Captain Thakuri served our country through his music until his final days after being assign as a DSP with the Uttar Pradesh Police's Provincial Arms Constabulary (PAC) band. One of the lesser-known but possibly most important events in the Indian Freedom Movement was the Naval Uprising in 1946. At this time, the Indian Navy men in Bombay and Karachi revolted against the British. More than 20,000 mutineers joined the Freedom Fighters from Karachi to Calcutta after being inspire by the Indian National Army. Other personnel of the army, air force, and even citizens were motivated to join the demonstrations by this. Navy man Puspa Kumar Ghising from Darjeeling fought with at least three British soldiers during the uprising and was able to seize control of the Bombay naval weapons stockpile by himself. The rebellious Indian sailors used the munitions dump's armaments to hold the British at bay for five days. On the sixth day, however, the Indian National Congress leaders stepped in and persuaded the sailors to surrender. After being detain along with his companions, Ghising was court-martialled but found not guilty at the trial in Mulundi Jail. On September 8, 1946, he left the Navy and became involved in the independence struggle. Many modern historians believe that the naval rebellion was the crucial event that

- accelerated the British decision to leave India, despite the fact that it has not received the same recognition in the history books as other significant events in the Freedom Movement. On August 15, 1989, the government presented Ghising with the Tamra Patra in appreciation of his contributions to the Independence movement.
- b. **Helen Lepcha – Sikkim and Kurseong:** Helen Lepcha, the sole female Sikkim freedom warrior, was born in South Sikkim in 1902. The family moved to Kurseong in pursuit of better educational and employment opportunities. As a volunteer during the 1920 Bihar floods, Helen Lepcha gave unceasing assistance to the victims, drawing Mahatma Gandhi's notice. In recognition of her dedication to the people, Gandhi dubbed her Sabitri Devi. Helen Lepcha strengthened the Freedom Movement by working with coal workers from the coalfields in what was then Bihar and among workers in the United Provinces (Uttar Pradesh). Supporting the Freedom campaign and taking part in the non-cooperation campaign in 1921. She was later imprisoned for "inciting the people against the government" and placed under house detention and jail for three months. Helen Lepcha was instrumental in sneaking coded messages in and out of Giddhey Pahar in Kurseong during Netaji's house detention in 1939–1940. This helped pave the way for Netaji's eventual escape from Calcutta to Germany, directly in front of the British police.
- c. **Major Durga Malla – Uttarakhand:** Durga Malla was born in Doiwala village in Uttarakhand Dehradun district on July 1, 1913, and enlisted in the Gorkha Rifles in 1931 at the age of 18. At the height of World War II, in 1942, a group of Indian soldiers under Durga Malla made the decision to secede and establish the Indian National Army, which was commanded by Netaji Subhas Chandra Bose. One of the main players in the INA's founding was Durga Malla, who played a major role in persuading other Gorkha soldiers to defect from the British and join the INA because he played a major role in persuading other Gorkha soldiers to defect from the British and join the INA. Given his commitment to India's independence and his military prowess, Netaji elevated him to the rank of Major and assigned him to the INA's intelligence division, where he excelled and frequently took on dangerous tasks that advanced the INA. The Indian government with a Tamra Patra citation honoured her. On March 27, 1944, he was caught near Urkhul, Manipur, and while on one of these intelligence-gathering trips. He was detained as a prisoner of war at the Red Fort along with other INA inmates. He flatly refused to bow

before the British there, despite their attempts to get him to renounce INA and their assurance that doing so would save his life. When the British tried to persuade him to condemn INA, they summoned his wife, Smt. Sharda Devi, but he informed her, "Sharda, I am sacrificing my life for the freedom of my motherland." "You do not have to feel anxious or upset. After I go, you will have crores of Hindustanis. My offering of sacrifice will not be in vain. India will be liberated. It is just a question of time, I am sure. He was hang on the gallows on August 25, 1944. His statue, which honor the Gorkha community's commitment to our independence, is now display on the grounds of our parliament.

- d. **Subedar Niranjan Singh Chettri– Manipur:** The distinction of being the first Gorkhali to be slain for our homeland belongs to Subedar Niranjan Singh Chettri ji of Manipur, who is a member of the legendary Gorkha community, which has produced numerous heroes for our country. Niranjan Chettri, 39, of Tikumoh, a former army Sipahi of the 34th native Infantry, joined the native force of Manipur under the command of Bir Tikendra Jit and Thangal General when the great Manipuri hero Jubraj Tikendra Jit Singh made the decision to oppose the British intrusions into Manipur. Jubraj Tikendra selected him as Subedar because of his military experience and gallantry. The British hanged him on June 8, 1891, after being tried by the Chief Political Officer of the Manipur Field Force after the war. "My Motherland is my birthplace, and I am willing to die and kill for this land, but I am not prepared to accept surrender and subjugation of my own land," he said in his final words. His sacrifice had been relegate to the annals of history for decades. Nonetheless, the history and legacy of this renowned Gorkha independence fighter are at last being reveal under Chief Minister N Biren Singh. Chief Minister Singh recognized the contribution of Shaheed Subedar Niranjan Singh Chettri by stating, "I am so happy to unveil the statue of Shaheed Subedar Niranjan Singh Chettri, one of the heroes of Anglo-Manipur War, 1891." The statue was unveiled on March 7, 2021. He was unmatched in his bravery, patriotism, and attitude of selflessness for the country. On June 8, 1891, the British executed him by hanging due to his involvement in the conflict.
- e. **Dalbir Singh Lohar – Assam:** In 1921, Dalbir Singh Lohar, an Assamese, became involved in the freedom fight while Gandhi ji was in Dibrugarh. Along with other Gorkha freedom fighters from Assam, such as Bhakta Bahadur Pradhan and Anantalal Sharma,

he was imprisoned from 1930 to 31 for his involvement in the Civil Disobedience Movement. He was a labour leader and one of the most well-known Assamese freedom fighters, leading the Civil Disobedience Movement in Dibrugarh. The oldest refinery in Asia and the cradle of India's oil industry, located in Digboi, Assam, had a historic strike in 1939. One of the main organizers of the strike that the non-unionized workers of the Digboi Oil Refinery called was Dalbir Singh Lohar. The British crushed the Digboi walkout with an iron fist, sending down eight platoons of Assam Rifles to do so, citing tensions with Germany. The British gave all of the notable leaders, including Dalbir Singh Lohar, 72 hours' warning before issuing them Quit Digboi, Quit Lakhimpur, and lastly Quit Assam. During Gandhi Ji's Quit India Movement, he was captured once more, along with all the Gorkha freedom fighters, including Bhakta Bahadur Pradhan and Anant Lal Sharma, and they were all imprisoned separately, but they quickly came to represent the working class's opposition to the British government. With an overwhelming victory in the 1951 election, Dalbir Singh Lohar became the first Gorkha MLA elected from the Digboi Assembly following independence. Throughout his life, he remained dedicated to helping the working class. I have only highlighted a handful of their efforts today. There are hundreds of additional people who have contributed significantly to our independence, but there is not enough room to accommodate them all. As is evident, the Gorkhas, regardless of the state in which they were born, have been instrumental in our freedom struggles. As we commemorate "Azadi ka Amrit Mahotsav," I hope that more people nationwide will learn about heroes like them. "Jai Hind."

49. **Ayo Gorkhali: The war cry that has done every Gorkhali proud:** The 125th anniversary of 2/5 GR (FF), also known as VC Paltan, or 2nd Battalion of 5th Gorkha Rifles, Border Force, was commemorated. Because of the three Victoria Crosses that the British Army gave his soldiers during the World War II Burma campaign, this renowned battalion is known as the VC Paltan. Since no other battalion in any formation has won the country's highest gallantry medal three times, this achievement is unmatched in military history. The British used the 2/5 GR (FT), which was raised at Abbottabad in 1886, to keep the insurgent North West Frontier Province on control. He received three Victoria Crosses in Burma during World War II and laurels in Mesopotamia and Gallipoli during World War I. After India gained its independence, the battalion participated in every conflict including the UN mission in Congo. Along with several Gorkha veterans, Lieutenant General Vijay Ahluwalia, GOC-in-C, Central Command, was

present at the festivities at Almore. With the spine-tingling battle cry "Jai Mahakali, Ayo Gorkhali" (Victory to Goddess Mahakali, the Gorkhas are coming), the Gorkhas have distinguished themselves in nearly two centuries of service, first with the British Indian Army and later with the Indian Army. More than 200,000 of them served in the two World Wars; 43,000 of them gave their lives. The Gorkhas, who are primarily from the villages of poor hill farmers in Nepal's Gorkha district, are members of four major ethnic groups: the Rai and Limbus from the east, the Gurungs and Magars from the centre. Because of their exceptional resilience and toughness, the British had classified the Gorkhas as a "martial race." The Gorkha soldier's fierceness and unwavering bravery in combat have earned him international renown. The Gorkhas are "small of stature, large of heart, accustomed to hardship, good-natured with a keen sense of humour loyal to death, more disciplined than any fighting force in the world, brave and capable and absolutely without fear," according to one book. Unquestionably, these resilient soldiers are strong, fearless, and resilient in the face of fading fire. They are also incredibly disciplined. Each battalion's strong familial bonds guarantee that they fight for both their own family and the paltan's izzat. The slogan of the Gorkha troops, who continue to serve with pride and high-level professionalism in the British, Indian, and Nepalese military, is "Kafir hunu bhanda marnu jati" (better to die than be a coward). Throughout both World Wars, the British Indian Army's Gorkha battalions were crucial. They received war honor all across the world and witnessed action in Africa, Europe, and Asia. Four Gorkha regiments—the second, 6th, 7th, and 10th regiments—were transferred to the British Army after Partition in 1947 as part of a tripartite agreement between Britain, India, and Nepal. Eventually, these regiments became the Gorkha Brigade. Six (the first, third, fourth, fifth, eighth, and ninth regiments) of the ten entered the Indian Army, while the eleventh GR was established subsequently. The Indian Army now has seven Gurkha regiments with 39 battalions. The Nepalese Gorkha has contributed to the development of close friendships between the two armies, even though Gorkhas in the Indian Army are from both Nepal and the hill regions of India. The fifth Gorkha Rifles has a legendary past, despite the fact that all Gorkha regiments have served admirably in India's wars since independence. In 1948, the 5/5 GR (FF) bravely participated in the Hyderabad Police Action. On September 15, 1948, Naik Nar Bahadur Thapa received the first Ashok Chakra Class I of independent India for this deed. In the 1971 battle for Bangladesh's freedom, the 4/5 GR (FF) had the distinction of being the first Indian Army battalion to take part in a hellebore attack at the Battle of Sylhet. In addition to the major conflicts, the Gorkhas have participated in UN

peacekeeping operations in Lebanon and Sierra Leone, as well as in Bangladesh, Sri Lanka, and the Siachen Glacier. The 4/9 GR took home the gold prize from the annual Cambrian Patrol Competition in Wales, UK, in October 2011. The Gorkhas continue to use traditional weapons on the battlefield, such as the "Khukri," a large knife with a broad blade and a cruel curve that is 18 inches long. It is the most well-known fighting knife in the world. An unsheathed Khukri is believed to "frequently cause a cold, cramped feeling in the nether regions of the stomach, which is enough to discourage any further action." According to legend, a Khukri must "taste blood" after being brought into combat. Its owner had to cut himself before putting it back in its sheath if it did not.

50. Ayo Gorkhali (The Gurkhas are upon you) is the battle cry of one of the world's famous hands of fighting men: Nepal's 'happy warriors':

"In his famous statement about the Gorkhas, Field Marshal Sam Manekshaw, a former chief of army staff in the Indian Army (formerly of the 8th Gorkha Rifles Regiment), immortalized their military advantage and redefined conventional warfare: "If a man says he is not afraid of dying, he is either lying or is a Gorkha." Despite their widespread celebration, there are very few books on the Gorkhas that are authored by members of the group. In addition to giving readers a thorough account of their special place in history with his new book, *Ayo Gorkhali: A History of Gurkhas*, Tim I. Gurung, a native of mid-western Nepal and a former member of the British Army Gorkhas, deserves recognition for being among the first to publish the unvarnished voices of veteran Gorkhas. The author is successful in bringing to life the experiences of people who bravely served the flag of a nation other than their own through anecdotes and profiles, preserving the warrior traditions of their native countries in both word and spirit. The Gorkhas' story is not just one of valour and soldiering. Gurung's book gives readers a deep understanding of the Gorkha people's history while also telling the tale of a little society that made a significant contribution to world history. Serving in the armies of Nepal, India, and the united monarchy, the Gorkhas of Nepal are well-known for their distinctive contribution to world history. They assisted Prithvi Narayan Shah in establishing a strong monarchy in Gorkha. Starting in 1767, this event influenced Nepal's future course and ultimately resulted in a republic. Gurung, an insider, presents the Gorkhas' hardships and the motivations for

their mastery of the art of war with clarity. He did wind up in the army because he wanted a respectable and dignified life away from her feudal rule. They were force to dwell in isolated areas of Nepal, particularly in the early 19th century. The Gorkha kingdom looked to the British Empire in 1793 to defend itself from a Chinese invasion via Tibet. In 1793, he visited Nepal as part of the first British mission, and in 1802, he returned. Cooperation, however, was short-lived as disputes among the Gorkhas emerged regarding the dubious role of the British mission. The Gorkha Kingdom and the British East India Company, who had clear territorial aspirations, fought each other in the Anglo-Nepalese War (1814–1816) because of the new formation. The war concluded when the British won and signed the Treaty of Sugauli on March 4, 1816. Nepal distanced itself from the conquered lands west of the Kali River to the Sutlej River and gave up its territorial claims to the majority of the Terai (low-lying country) with the Treaty of Sugauli. Although Nepal managed to keep its independence, it was force to be supervise by a British resident (protectorate) who had the position of ambassador to the sovereign nation. Nepal was successful in keeping British citizens from acting as "controlling agents" for the British East India Company, which dominated India, its immediate neighbour, in spite of the agreement. In 1814, British General Sir David Ochterlony suggested pacifying the Gorkhas and enlisting them in the British Empire's armed forces. When the terrified British Empire learned of the Gorkhas' valour during the Gorkha War, the Gorkhas started to enlist in the Indian and British troops. In Sikkim, Nepal, ancient British cannons that were taken by the Gorkhas can still be found. All of these events are summarize for readers in this book. The Gorkhas have had a challenging transition over the years because of shifting geostrategic factors. The concept of "enlightened self-interest" has a greater influence on Nepal's foreign and strategic policy as a new republic and a well establish democracy, marking a distinct shift from the royal era. It is visible to you. He formally expressed satisfaction with the Gorkhas' significant presence in both the Indian and British troops. There were no system fluctuations even with the new system. Gorkha war veterans face challenges in receiving pensions in their home countries, similar to many other concerns. However, with the help of Indian and Nepali governments, this issue must also be made simpler. Based on field research and first-hand recollections from former Gorkha veterans, Gurung presents a genuine picture. With a federal structure, a population that is extremely ethnically diverse, a long and proud history, and a notable Gorkha presence, Nepal is a developed democracy. The role that Gorkhas play in protecting India's borders is, in fact, a crucial component of the close bilateral ties between India and Nepal. Since Nepal's literary scene is

thriving, more authors ought to take a step back, consider their nation's past, and write about it. A position in the common awareness for history is crucial.

Conclusion:As in the real world, it is "better to die than to live as a coward"; the Gorkhas' identity was shaped by their sheer masculinity during the conflict. Their extraordinary bravery holds a significant place in the history of the entire globe, not just Nepal and Britain. The Gorkhas lost the Anglo-Nepalese war, but their unwavering bravery and devotion prevented colonization of Nepal. Additionally, the British East India Company recruited them into its army due to their strong manhood during the Anglo-Nepalese War. They were successful in exploiting Indian society's banditry and revolt, which posed a serious challenge to the British administration. The Gorkhas participated in both World Wars I and II, and their triumphs helped to popularize their masculinity globally. Actually, it was their hyperactive, high-level masculinity. Gorkha masculinity was crucial to Britain's success in the war in the Falkland Islands as well as in battles and military operations on Borneo and the Malay Peninsula. The Victoria Cross and other decorations they were awarded for their valour throughout the conflict further evidence the Gorkhas' hyperactive masculinity. The Gorkhas' super-gallantry and hyper-masculinity in the globe are vividly shown in the book *Imperial Warriors: Britain and the Gurkhas by Could*. In addition to being valiant in combat, the Gorkhas are also known for saving civilians, officers, and other combatants. Their bravery in "fighting" and "saving" during numerous conflicts, including the Anglo-Nepalese War, World War I, and World War II, is evident. The water supply to Kalanga Fort had to be shut off during the Anglo-Nepalese War, making it extremely difficult for well-trained and equipped British forces to overcome the Gorkhas. The Gorkha troops only committed such heinous acts because their defeated mentality overcame their war heroism. Following the Gorkhas' enlistment in the British East India Army, people were released from the typical issues of mutiny and banditry, while British officers were shielded from insurgents. During World Wars I and II, the Gorkhas fought valiantly for the British. They maintained the Union Jack's positive reputation throughout the world by beating their adversaries. They received many awards, including the Victoria Cross, for their valiant rescue operations and valiant battles. The Gorkhas still had to contend with insurgent elements in Borneo and Malaya following World War II. They exploited the rebellion to save the citizens and leaders of each nation. For a considerable amount of time during the Falklands War, the Gorkhas did not fight alongside the Argentine army since the soldiers swiftly gave up after learning about the Gorkhas' valour. During the imperial and post-imperial periods, the Gorkhas

were the primary factor in British triumphs in numerous wars waged all over the world. To sum up, Mr. Gurung's book "Ayo Gorkhas: A History of the Gurkhas" eloquently illustrates the Gorkhas' "double heroism" during the conflict: "fighting" and "saving."

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